

Report on Research Line 4

Environmental Sustainability and Vulnerability: Cases of Micro-Enterprises led by Disadvantaged Entrepreneurs

Insights from ACCTING's Experimental Research

Research Cycle 2

Author: Gabriele Quinti (K&I)

Contributors: Francesca Pugliese (K&I), Alain Denis (YW), Aart Kerremans (YW), Giuseppe Pellegrini Masini (NTNU), Kenneth Vilhelmsen (NTNU), Vassilis Chatzibirros (SEERC), Christos Stergiadis (SEERC), Andrei Holman (UAIC), Simona Popusoi (UAIC)

Reviewers: Gabor Szudi (ZSI), Carolin Zorell (ORU), Sofia Strid (UGOT)

Please cite as: Quinti, G., Pugliese, F., Denis, A., Kerremans, A., Pellegrini Masini, G., Vilhelmsen, K., Chatzibirros, V., Stergiadis, C., Holman, A., & Popusoi, S. (2025). ACCTING Report on Research Line 4: Environmental Sustainability and Vulnerability: Cases of Micro-Enterprises led by Disadvantaged Entrepreneurs. Zenodo. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15525858

The ACCTING project

It is acknowledged by now that the global climate crisis is not only an ecological crisis but also an economic, social and political crisis, with devastating effects on individuals and societies. These negative effects are not evenly distributed within societies. It is the poorer, marginalised and vulnerable groups who are the most acutely affected, exacerbating existing socio-economic inequalities. The European Green Deal foresees efficient use of resources for a circular and clean economy. However, inequalities emerge in the context of its policy and interventions.

The EU-funded ACCTING project takes these considerations as a starting point for a complex series of research and experimental activities aimed at identifying, analysing and testing policies and initiatives capable of responding to this crisis, mitigating its effects on the most vulnerable and helping them play a significant role in the pursuit of greater environmental sustainability.

The project mobilises research experimentation and innovation to promote an inclusive and socially just European Green Deal focusing on the inequalities produced by its policies and supporting behavioural change at individual and collective levels.

ACCTING explores the impact of Green Deal policy initiatives on individual and collective behaviours, provides evidence, and empowers policymakers and stakeholders to anticipate policy responses and potential negative influences, and mitigate such impacts in decision-making. The project collects new data on Green Deal policy interventions and co-designs and implements pilot actions to reduce or prevent policy-related inequalities and advance behavioural change for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal.

Acknowledgment of funding

The ACCTING project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation under grant agreement no. 101036504.

Disclaimer

The information, documentation and figures in this deliverable are written by the ACCTING project consortium and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Table of contents

Table of contents	3
List of tables	4
Introduction and methodology	5
1. Introduction, case study selection and access	5
1.1 Sustainability and transformation in the context of the RL4.....	5
1.2 Behavioural change in the context of the RL4.....	5
1.3 Research design, the choice of cases, and the study participants recruitment	6
1.3.4 Vulnerability, marginalisation and disadvantage from a gender+ intersectional perspective reflected among the (groups of) study participants	16
2. Methodology and study materials	17
2.1 General research design is put in practice and the choice of methods.....	17
2.2 The study material used for data collection (and measurements of relevant variables).....	23
Analysis and Results	25
3. Data collected and analysis	25
3.1 Steps and timeframe of data collection	25
3.2 Overview of the sample statistic(s) of participants in the RL4 case studies....	25
3.3 Results of the individual case studies and the country studies.....	26
3.3.2 Advanced analysis (Outcome analysis)	37
Conclusions and Discussions	57
4. Overall conclusions and discussion	57
4.1 Overall conclusions with respect to the RL specific research question.....	57
4.2 Overall conclusions with respect to implementing a gender+ inclusive Green Deal	61
4.3 Expected sustainability of impacts and changes measured	62
4.4 Replicability and scalability of the actions studied.....	62
4.5 Policy crossovers.....	62
4.6 Research Limitations: A critical discussion of the choice of cases and research design.....	63
4.7 Discussion of research gaps and avenues for future research.....	64
References	66

List of tables

Table 1: Vulnerability grounds of the recruited micro-entrepreneurs per country.....	16
Table 2: Economic sectors covered by the micro-enterprises per country.....	18
Table 3: Environmental measures adopted by the micro-entrepreneurs per country.....	20
Table 4: Determinants of the outcome – Belgium.....	27
Table 5: Determinants of the outcome – Greece.....	28
Table 6: Determinants of the outcome – Italy.....	29
Table 7: Determinants of the outcome – Norway	31
Table 8: Determinants of the outcome – Romania	32
Table 9: Presence and intensity of the determinants of outcome in the 21 cases, by country	33
Table 10: Outcome by vulnerability factor	38
Table 11: Outcome by educational level	39
Table 12: Outcome by micro-enterprise turnover	40
Table 13: Outcome by motivation	40
Table 14: Outcome by micro-entrepreneurs’ values.....	44
Table 15: Outcome by inclusion in networks.....	44
Table 16: Outcome by micro-enterprise type of crisis	45
Table 17: Outcome by personal behaviour/Individual change	47
Table 18: Enablers (+) and hindrances (-) per type and country	50
Table 19: Enablers (+) and hindrances (-) related to Resources, per country.....	50
Table 20: Enablers (+) and hindrances (-) related to Social dynamics, per country.....	53
Table 21: Enablers (+) and hindrances (-) related to Structural conditions, per country ...	55
Table 22: Enablers (+) and hindrances (-) related to Structural conditions, per country ...	63

Introduction and methodology

1. Introduction, case study selection and access

This report presents a summary of findings from Research Line 4 of ACCTING's second cycle of experimental studies, which draws on data gathered from 87 quasi-experimental case studies conducted across thirteen countries between December 2023 and August 2024. Each research line explores sustainability and behavioural change within the framework of a specific European Green Deal policy area—including climate change, biodiversity, energy, food, and transport. This report focuses on *energy and more broadly on the environmental sustainability of micro-enterprises led by disadvantaged people*, examining how policies can support vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs.

All reports are available at <https://accting.eu/project-deliverables/>

1.1 Sustainability and transformation in the context of the RL4

Sustainability in the Research Line 4 (RL4) refers to environmental sustainability with a particular, but not exclusive, reference to the energy transition. In fact, in the second cycle, RL4 looks at vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who have set on a journey towards environmental sustainability in their business by adopting or at least designing measures:

- In the area of energy transition (such as the set-up of photovoltaic panels, software systems to reduce energy consumption, better thermal insulation, optimisation of transport and mobility, use of high-efficiency energy equipment, reduction in emissions from crops/livestock), or
- In other environmental areas (such as minimisation of packaging and plastics, use of biodegradable materials, minimisation of food waste, use of eco-sustainable products, separate waste collection practices).

Transformation in RL4 refers to the changes that have characterised the micro-enterprises' business on their way towards environmental sustainability, thanks to the measures adopted both during the observation period (November 2023-June 2024) and before (in principle, the year before). As will be seen later (see Section 2.1), thanks to the research design adopted in this research cycle, ACCTING itself may have generated transformations within the micro-enterprises included in this RL.

1.2 Behavioural change in the context of the RL4

The behavioural change which is the primary focus of the second cycle of this research line refers to the behavioural change of each micro-entrepreneur both in the way they lead their business and in their everyday life, based on the above-mentioned transformations (measures towards environmental sustainability).

The second focus is the behavioural change of individuals working with the micro-entrepreneurs, such as their employees and associates. An additional focus is the milieu of the micro-entrepreneur, and particularly the clients, since in some cases (bars, restaurants, tailor's shops, etc.), they may condition the pro-environmental choices of the entrepreneurs; for example, when measures involve an increase in prices.

1.3 Research design, the choice of cases, and the study participants recruitment

1.3.1 Research design

The European Green Deal recognises the key role SMEs can and should play in the transition towards a more sustainable future¹. However, while some SMEs are really engaged in this direction², many other SMEs (and even more micro-enterprises³, led by people in vulnerable conditions) are extraneous to this process⁴, both because those who manage them have often no or little awareness of climate change issues, and because – if they have – they come up against multiple obstacles (lack of resources and skills, lack of incentives and assistance from third parties, etc.).

This is not an easy issue to research as it is very difficult to reach the (most) vulnerable entrepreneurs; especially those who have done little or nothing in terms of energy efficiency measures or, more broadly, environmental sustainability. As seen in the recruitment phase during RC1, these micro-entrepreneurs try to be as inconspicuous as possible (e.g., they do not belong to networks and keep their relationships to a minimum). So, they are often ‘hidden’ and if they are not, they are not available anyway.

On the other hand, those who are doing, or at least planning to do something to improve the environmental sustainability of their business are sometimes more open to consultation (albeit with many difficulties, as mentioned above). Therefore, it was decided to try to focus on the latter, i.e., the vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who have started (or at least planned) a change process towards improving the environmental sustainability of their business.

It is worth noting that this was not just a choice made out of necessity. As ACCTING’s objectives include “to prevent inequalities, and produce knowledge and innovations to advance behavioural change at individual and collective levels for an inclusive and equal European Green Deal”, it was in fact considered more profitable to bet on the existence of these micro-entrepreneurs who, despite their vulnerable conditions (perhaps often exacerbated by the context in which they work), nevertheless (for one reason or another, as will be seen later) address the issue of environmental sustainability. Against this backdrop, the aim was to identify how this group of entrepreneurs can successfully tackle this challenge and successfully make their businesses environmentally sustainable (i.e., achieve a ‘positive outcome’, as explained later in Section 2.1); how they change their behaviour in managing their businesses; and what obstacles and facilitating factors they encounter along the way. In addition, the focus is also on the adoption (or not) of more sustainable behaviour in the personal lives of micro-entrepreneurs or their potential collaborators (partners, employees) and their milieu (e.g., their customers).

¹ <https://www.sme-enterprize.com/news/video/european-green-deal-propelling-smes-into-a-green-future-through-eco-innovation/>

² Palm, J. (2009). Placing barriers to industrial energy efficiency in a social context: a discussion of lifestyle categorisation. *Energy Efficiency*, 2(3), 263–270. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12053-009-9042-1>

³ Microenterprises are defined as enterprises employing fewer than 10 persons whose annual turnover or annual balance sheet total does not exceed EUR 2 million (Articles 3 to 6 of Annex I to Commission Regulation (EU) No 651/2014 (27)). According to Eurostat's Structural Business Statistics, the share of microenterprises in total net turnover in Europe is significant: almost 17% at EU level. Eurostat, 2024. Enterprise statistics by size class and NACE. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/sbs_sc_ovw_custom_11310719/default/table?lang=en. The share of microenterprises in EU industries' ecosystems is very important (e.g. 87% in the agri-food sector; 89% in Textile; 92% in Tourism; 94% in construction; 94,5% in digital). See Di Bella, L. et al., 2023. Annual Report on European SMEs, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union.

⁴ INNOVEAS (H2020) (<https://innoveas.eu>). Deliverable 2.2 “Assessment of non-technical barriers”; June 2020.

So, the research question was drafted as follows: “How do the most vulnerable entrepreneurs (i.e. those with whom one or more vulnerability criteria can be associated from an intersectional approach – see below) change their behaviour in the management of their enterprises, and broadly, towards climate change mitigation in connection to the planning and adoption of pro-environmental measures? Which are the enabling and the hindering factors in this process?”

At first glance, it might seem that this is not an innovative research question. In fact, there are many studies and a large literature on how some SMEs deal with environmental sustainability issues (with a specific but not exclusive focus on energy efficiency and the transition to renewable energy), looking at, among other things, the barriers and drivers that SMEs encounter⁵. Some studies also focus on entrepreneurs who have shown interest and real commitment in this area (they could be considered success stories)⁶.

However, most of these studies concern SMEs in general, and only a few focus specifically on micro-enterprises; and very few concern Europe⁷, while other geographical contexts seem to receive more attention⁸. We can also specify that, according to the IEECP (Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy) “there is no dedicated research on barriers to energy transition and in particular energy efficiency measures in micro-enterprises⁹”.

Finally, it does not appear that any of these studies pay attention to micro-enterprises run by vulnerable people. Rather, the literature on vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs seems to be concerned with other issues (e.g., how much and how micro-enterprises may or may not support certain categories of disadvantaged people; how functional they may or may not be in terms of poverty alleviation¹⁰; how micro-enterprises training programmes may instead reinforce segregation; the

⁵ Crehan P. (2021). A Business Service Ecosystem Supporting the Transition to Net Zero, presented at The ISPIM Innovation Conference – Innovating Our Common Future, Berlin, Germany on 20–23 June 2021. Proceedings by LUT Scientific and Expertise Publications; Johansson, M.T., & Thollander, P. (2018). A review of barriers to and driving forces for improved energy efficiency in Swedish industry—recommendations for successful in-house energy management. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 618–628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.052>; Meath, C., Linnenluecke, M., & Griffiths, A. (2015). Barriers and motivators to the adoption of energy savings measures for SMEs: The case of the ClimateSmart Business Cluster Program. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112(5), 3597–3604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.08.085>; Nulkar, G. (2014). SMEs and environmental performance—A framework for green business strategies. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133, 130–140. Available at: <https://pdf.sciencedirectassets.com/277811/1-s2.0-S1877042814X00297/1-s2.0-S1877042814030870/main.pdf>; Sorrell, S., Mallett, A., & Nye, S. (2011). Barriers to industrial energy efficiency: A literature review. UNIDO. www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0928765516302846; Thollander, P., Backlund, S., Trianni, A., & Cagno E. (2013). Beyond barriers – A case study on driving forces for improved energy efficiency in the foundry industries in Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Sweden. *Applied Energy*, 111, 636–643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.05.036>; Trianni, A., Cagno, E., & Farné, S. (2016). Barriers, drivers and decision-making process for industrial energy efficiency: A broad study among manufacturing small and medium-sized enterprises. *Applied Energy*, 162, 1537–1551. DOI: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.02.078; Triguero, A., Moreno-Mondéjar, L., & Davia, M.A. (2011). Drivers of different types of eco-innovation in European SMEs. *Ecological Economics*, 92, 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.04.009> al. 2016; Hrovatin et al. 2016.

⁶ Palm, J. (2009). Placing barriers to industrial energy efficiency in a social context: a discussion of lifestyle categorisation. *Energy Efficiency*, 2(3), 263–270. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s12053-009-9042-1>

⁷ Hitchens, D., Thankappan, S., Trainor, M., Clausen, J., & De Marchi, B. (2005). Environmental performance, competitiveness and management of small businesses in Europe. *Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie*, 96(5), 541–557. Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/4920778_Environmental_performance_competitiveness_and_management_of_small_businesses_in_Europe; Corsini, F., Appio, F. P., & Frey, M. (2019). Exploring the antecedents and consequences of environmental performance in microenterprises: The case of the Italian craft beer industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, 340–350.

⁸ Gurung P., Sarkar S. (2022). Sustainability of Microenterprises: An Empirical Investigation. June 2022. *Indian Journal of Economics*. Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372751525_Sustainability_of_Microenterprises_An_Empirical_Investigation.

⁹ Rogulj I. (2024). Discussion paper: What determinants of microenterprises influence their energy vulnerability? IEECP.

¹⁰ Lateh, M., Hussain, M. D., & Halim, M. S. A. (2017). Micro enterprise development and income sustainability for poverty reduction: A literature investigation. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, 7(1), 23–38.

functions of social media; the impact of crises such as the Covid-19 pandemic), referring to micro-enterprises run by certain categories of disadvantaged people: women's micro-enterprises¹¹, youth micro-enterprises¹² and micro-enterprises promoted by migrants¹³. Some references are also made to the notion of intersectionality (e.g., gender and migrant background¹⁴).

Our research question could therefore have considerable novelty, as it touches on areas of research that are not always in contact with each other: environmental sustainability of European micro-enterprises, micro-enterprises run by intersectional vulnerable groups, and their environmental sustainability.

1.3.2 Context of the case-studies

21 case studies, each corresponding to a vulnerable micro-entrepreneur and their business, were included in the second cycle of the RL4.

- 5 in the areas of Liège, Antwerp and Brussels (Belgium)
- 4 in Thessaloniki (Greece)
- 4 in Rome (Italy)
- 4 in Trondheim (Norway)
- 4 in Iași (Romania).

The country contexts, with specific reference to the issue of environmental sustainability in micro-enterprises run by disadvantaged people, exhibit both similarities and differences.

- All countries are in Europe (albeit one not in the EU), in different regional contexts (two in the Balkans, one in the South-West, one in the North and the last one in Scandinavia, in the extreme North).

¹¹ Revenga, A., & Dooley, M. (2020). What works for women micro entrepreneurs. A Meta-analysis of Recent Evaluations to Support Female Entrepreneurship. Available at: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/what-works-for-women-microentrepreneurs>; Ehlers, T. B., & Main, K. (1998). Women and the false promise of microenterprise. *Gender & Society*, 12(4), 424-440; Aracil-Jordá, J., Clemente-Almendros, J. A., Jiménez-Zarco, A. I., & González-González, I. (2023). Improving the social performance of women-led microenterprises: The role of social media marketing actions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 191, 122484; Crittenden, V. L., Crittenden, W. F., & Ajjan, H. (2019). Empowering women microentrepreneurs in emerging economies: The role of information communications technology. *Journal of Business Research*, 98, 191-203. Arul Paramanandam, D., & Packirisamy, P. (2015). An empirical study on the impact of micro enterprises on women empowerment. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 9(4), 298-314.

¹² Khan, S. J. M. (2020). 5 Youth Entrepreneurship in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). *Talent Development for Youth Entrepreneurship* (UUM Press), 101; Shahzady, R. (2024). The Role of Social-Media for Microentrepreneurship of Young Startups. *International Journal of Law and Policy*, 2(6), 10-22; Tessema, G. (2015). Assessing the challenges of youth entrepreneurship in micro and small-scale enterprises: the case of North Gondar zone, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(12), 53-64.

¹³ Harima A (2022). Transnational migration entrepreneurship during a crisis: Immediate response to challenges and opportunities emerging through the COVID-19 pandemic. *Business and Society Review* 127(S1): 223–251; Rahman MZ, Ullah F, Thompson P (2018) Challenges and issues facing ethnic minority small business owners: The Scottish experience. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation* 19(3): 177–193.

¹⁴ David, A., Terstriep, J., Schäfer, S., & Schmidt, A. G. (2024). An intersectional perspective on the impacts and responses of entrepreneurs during the COVID-19 pandemic in Germany. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 14657503241258933; Lassalle P, Shaw E (2021) Trailing wives and constrained agency among women migrant entrepreneurs: An intersectional perspective. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice* 45(6): 1496–1521. See also (among other). Qureshi, I., Bhatt, B., Sutter, C., & Shukla, D. M. (2023). Social entrepreneurship and intersectionality: Mitigating extreme exclusion. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 38(2), 106283; Mulira, F., & Ndaba, Z. (2016). Gender and disability: An intersectionality perspective of microenterprise learning among women with disabilities in Uganda. *Africagrowth Agenda*, 2016(10), 14-17.

- Two of the five countries have a fairly dynamic ‘business demography of micro-enterprises’ (births and deaths of micro-enterprises) (Italy with around 50,000 births and deaths per year and Romania with around 32,000 births and deaths per year), while in two others this dynamic is more limited (Greece and Norway with around 4,000 births and deaths and Belgium with less than 3,000)¹⁵.
- The adoption of energy efficiency and renewable energy measures in the business sector is high on the agenda in all countries. However, there are more policies targeted at large energy-intensive industries than at SMEs, especially micro-enterprises¹⁶. Indeed, the number of SMEs (and especially micro-companies) is disproportionate to their energy consumption (indeed, SMEs constitute 99% of companies in the EU, while their rate of energy consumptions, very difficult to calculate, is however much lower – eg. 47% in Italy and 16% in Austria)¹⁷, which is one of the reasons why they have not yet been a priority for energy transition measures¹⁸.
- Therefore, energy efficiency and renewable energy measures are not mandatory for SMEs (and even less so for micro-enterprises) but are strongly recommended. Obligatory energy audits for micro-companies are not cost-effective at this moment, but a walk-through audit could be considered. Moreover, the European Commission has established or supported multiple networks, projects and programmes assisting SMEs, like The Covenant of Companies for Climate and Energy¹⁹ (including advisory services for companies and intermediaries in energy transition; expertise and support materials; visibility, recognition and incentive schemes; effective monitoring, reporting and verification systems to verify company commitments; analysis of potential synergies between businesses and local authorities) or Enterprise Europe Network (world’s largest support network for SMEs)²⁰. However, the networks that exist in each country to support vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs, particularly those focusing on environmental issues, are relevant and strong in Belgium and Italy, almost non-existent in Norway and in an intermediate position in Greece and Romania.
 - In all countries, there are incentives (e.g., tax incentives such as tax deductions, accruals, tax breaks, subsidised interest rates or 0%-rates when applying for bank advances) and/or other opportunities (e.g., subsidies for certain purchases, project financing, non-repayable financing) for any company that wants to reduce its emissions (and all of this applies, broadly speaking, to Norway as well). Indeed, the actual way in which the incentives are operationalised and implemented varies widely, with some contexts (e.g., Belgium and Italy) appearing more favourable than others (e.g., Norway and Romania).

¹⁵ This also depends, of course, on the size of the countries, Italy and Romania being the two most populated countries: A considerable difference remains, however, even after relating this dynamic to the number of inhabitants of each country (per thousand inhabitants). The rates, thus derived, are as follows. Romania: 1.64; Italy: 0.85; Norway: 0.52; Greece: 0.38; Belgium: 0.35.

¹⁶ Rogulj I. (2024). Cit.

¹⁷ Herce, C., Biele, E., Martini, C., Salvio, M., Toro, C., Brandl, G. & Reuter, S. (2024). A methodology to characterize energy consumption in small and medium-sized enterprises at national level in European countries. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 26(1), 93-108.

¹⁸ Reuter, S., Lackner, P. & Brandl, G., 2021. Mapping SMEs in Europe: Data collection, analysis and methodologies for estimating energy consumptions at Country levels, s.l.: H2020 LEAP4SME.

¹⁹ <https://www.smeunited.eu/the-covenant-of-companies-for-climate-and-energy-ccce>

²⁰ Rogulj I. (2024). Cit.

- The level of progress of enterprises towards a green economy is most advanced in Norway, followed by Greece, and less advanced in Belgium, Italy and Romania²¹.

In addition, there are major differences between the socio-economic contexts of these five countries. In the tables below, the focus is on two issues that are all closely related to this RL: position on environmental sustainability and implementation of the Green Deal.

Belgium

<p>Political position on sustainability</p>	<p>Belgium has adopted the UN’s 17 SDGs, which falls under the responsibility of various public authorities. Belgium is a federal state composed of three communities and three regions, and the different levels of authority have varying competencies, including the Flemish government. This requires close coordination in relation to sustainability objectives and it can lead to fragmentation.</p>
<p>Implementation of the Green Deal</p>	<p>At the federal level, there is a Minister of Climate, Environment, Sustainable Development and Green Deal. At the Flemish level, there is a Minister responsible for the Environment, though there is less focus on sustainability or the Green Deal. Belgium’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan provides for investments towards a green transition in the areas of infrastructure and sustainable transport, clean and efficient generation of energy, and circular economy. According to recent reports, the Flemish region is not on course to achieve its 2030 climate goals (40% reduction in GHG emissions).</p>

Greece

<p>Political position on sustainability</p>	<p>Main actors are the Ministry of Environment & Energy and the Ministry of Development & Investment, encouraging the adoption of good sustainable development practices in the field of the green economy. The main economic policy actions proposed are to invest publicly and give incentives for private spending on the energy upgrading of buildings, to support flagship green development actions, as well as to develop infrastructure through public investment and prioritise private mobilisation. The programme “Saving 2021” is one of the flagship projects subsidised by the Recovery and Resilience Fund, aimed at improving the energy class of households by at least 3 energy categories by 2025 (over 30% primary energy savings). The investment includes separate incentives to support poor and vulnerable households in the form of a higher subsidy rate and a separate budget of 100 million euros.</p>
<p>Implementation of the Green Deal</p>	<p>The Recovery and Resilience Facility Coordination Agency is the lead national body tasked with the coordination and monitoring of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and is responsible for the efficient use of EU recovery funds deriving from the Next Generation EU and its fundamental instrument, the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). The plan is in line with the strategic priorities of Greece’s National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) and its specific targets. The NECP and Greece’s national plans in</p>

²¹ Cheba, K., Bąk, I., Szopik-Depczyńska, K., & Ioppolo, G. (2022). Directions of green transformation of the European Union countries. *Ecological Indicators*, 136, 108601.

	<p>Waste Management, Reforestation, Circular Economy and Biodiversity form the strategy underpinning the Recovery and Resilience Plan’s contribution to the green transition. The Circular Economy Action Plan aims to reduce waste and enhance the use of secondary materials, promote environmentally sustainable products and highlights those sectors that can contribute most to the achievement of circular economy objectives. The revised Waste Framework Directive sets targets for horizontal recycling of Municipal Solid Waste for 2025 (55%) and 2030 (60%), recycling by type of material in packaging waste and limiting landfill to 10% of managed waste by 2035.</p>
--	---

Italy

<p>Political position on sustainability</p>	<p>At the national level, the tool for coordinating the implementation of Agenda 2030 is the National Sustainable Development Strategy (NSDS), approved in 2017. It is a measure that provides for a three-year update and “defines the national reference framework for environmental and territorial planning, programming and evaluation processes to implement the sustainable development goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda.”</p>
<p>Implementation of the Green Deal</p>	<p>The implementation of the European Green Deal in Italy should be seen in the context of the implementation of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP). The responsibility for the implementation of the Italian NRRP is under the Presidency of the Council of Ministers and involves the various Ministries (as well as other public administrations) according to their areas of competence.</p>

Norway

<p>Political position on sustainability</p>	<p>Norway regards the 2030 Agenda with its 17 Sustainable Development Goals as a transformative global roadmap for national and international efforts aimed at eradicating extreme poverty while protecting planetary boundaries and promoting prosperity, peace and justice. The process of preparing Norway’s initial Voluntary National Review (VNR) to the High-Level Political Forum (HLPF) has contributed to greater political and public awareness about the SDGs in Norway. Each of the 17 goals have been identified for follow-up by the respective ministries that are mainly responsible for each goal in question. Each of these ministries have been tasked to coordinate with other ministries that are involved in the follow-up of the various targets under each goal, and to submit an account in its budget proposal on the status of follow-up for its respective goal(s). The Ministry of Finance will sum up the main points in the national budget, which is presented to the Storting annually, along with the state budget. This ensures annual reporting on the follow-up of SDGs to the Storting, in a well-established process.</p>
<p>Implementation of the Green Deal</p>	<p>Norway is outside the European Union. Nevertheless, in April 2023 the EU and Norway established a Green Alliance to strengthen their joint climate action, environmental protection efforts, and cooperation on the clean energy and industrial transition. Broadly speaking, Norway and the EU share a common regulatory framework within the Single Market and</p>

	Schengen, and they cooperate extensively in foreign and security policy (so, not in the fields related to environmental sustainability).
--	--

Romania

<p>Political position of sustainability</p>	<p>At the national level, the National Sustainable Development Strategy (NSDS) is the tool for coordinating the implementation of Agenda 2030; it was approved in 2017. It “defines the national reference framework for environmental and territorial planning, programming and evaluation processes to implement the sustainable development goals of the United Nations 2030 Agenda.” The main document guiding the national political position on sustainability is Romania’s National Sustainable Development Strategy 2030, adopted by the Romanian Government in 2018. It delineates the strategy of progressing at the national level towards the 17 SDGs proposed in the UN 2030 Agenda.</p>
<p>Implementation of the Green Deal</p>	<p>The GD implementation is set within the actions included in the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP), which proposes relevant investments and measures on six dimensions within its first pillar (“Green transition”): Water management, Forests and Biodiversity protection, Waste management, Sustainable transport, Renovation Wave (of commercial and residential buildings) and Energy. The implementation of the Romanian NRRP is administered and monitored by dedicated inter-ministerial committees.</p>

1.3.3 Gender+ intersectional criteria in the study context

In this section below some insights are summarised on the position on gender equality in the five countries involved in RL4.

Belgium	Belgium ranks 8 th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index. At the federal level, there is a Secretary of State for Gender Equality, Equal Opportunities and Diversity, though to what degree the issue of environmental sustainability plays a role in these responsibilities is unclear. At the Flemish level, there is a Minister of Equal Opportunities, though this seems to be a less prevalent domain on the regional level. Gender equality was a dimension taken into account in the official evaluation of Belgium’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan.
Greece	The National Action Plan “Promoting gender equality, preventing and combating gender-based violence-citizenship arrangements-provisions on local government elections-other provisions” and the ratification of the Council of Europe Convention on Preventing and Combating Violence Against Women and Domestic Violence (the Istanbul Convention) set the first framework in this direction. The creation of the legislative framework, however, is not enough to produce the desired results. A concerted effort is needed by all stakeholders to integrate gender equality into public policies, and to develop projects and actions. Greece ranks last in the EU in terms of the Gender Equality Index for 2020 (2018 data), remaining in the same position since 2010, despite the slight improvement in the index compared to 2010 and 2017.
Italy	Italy ranks 14 th in the EU on the Gender Equality Index. A Department of Equal Opportunity is incardinated in the Presidency of the Council of Ministers, called to coordinate regulatory and administrative initiatives in all matters pertaining to the design and implementation of equal opportunity policies. Since the new government took office, the department is also entrusted with the responsibility for family policies.
Norway	According to the 2020 Global Gender Gap Index Rating Report, Norway ranks second in gender parity. The country is one of the most gender-equal countries in the world in terms of economic participation and opportunity, educational attainment, health and survival and political empowerment. The Norwegian Department for Equality, Non-discrimination and International Affairs has sectoral and coordination responsibility for equality and non-discrimination policy.
Romania	Gender equality matters are administered at the national level by the National Agency for Equal Opportunities of Women and Men, integrated in the Ministry of Work and Social Protection. The agency aims to promote the principle of equal opportunities and treatment for women and men and ensures the active integration of equal opportunities in all national programmes and policies. Romania ranks 26 th in the EU on the gender equality index (54.4 points out of 100), 13.5 points below the European average. Its score had a small

increase of 3.6 points from 2010. In the 2022 Global Gender Gap Index, Romania took 90th place.

The policies of the countries included in RL4 pay more or less attention to women's micro-entrepreneurship, youth micro-entrepreneurship and micro-entrepreneurship promoted by migrants, as well as micro-enterprises in geographically isolated areas. There is no (or almost no) attention to other vulnerability profiles.

A few examples of policies/projects are listed below²².

- *Belgium*

- Supporting Entrepreneurship: Micro, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises²³.
- Women in Business Initiative²⁴.
- Regional support for aspiring migrant entrepreneurs in the Brussels region²⁵.
- MicroStart: integration of migrants in Brussels through entrepreneurship and self-employment²⁶.

- *Greece*

- The Greek Association of Women Entrepreneurs (SEGE), through the implementation of actions such as Consultancy, Education, Mentoring, etc., develops women's entrepreneurship and supports the sustainability of women's business²⁷.

- *Italy*

- Smart&Start Italia – Incentive for innovative start-ups, with a special focus on women's entrepreneurial initiatives. The programme aims to support high-tech projects and promote women's talent in the innovation sector²⁸.
- Lazio Region – Sustainable Agriculture – supports, among other things, the development of less-favoured areas and the promotion of women's entrepreneurship in the agricultural sector.
- Innovative investments in women's businesses in mountain communities, including innovative start-ups, mainly by women in small businesses (also for energy efficiency – environmental sustainability)²⁹.

²² These are opportunities that are not all active at the moment but have been active for longer or shorter periods, and in some cases permanently from 2021 onwards.

²³ <https://be.brussels/en/about-region/values-budget-and-strategy/strategy-and-policy-priorities/projects-political-priorities/strategic-goals-economy-and-entrepreneurship/supporting-entrepreneurship-micro-small-and-medium-sized-enterprises>

²⁴ <https://sheatwork.com/women-entrepreneurship-is-on-the-rise-in-belgium/>

²⁵ <https://info.hub.brussels/en/blog/regional-support-aspiring-migrant-entrepreneurs>

²⁶ https://coebank.org/documents/1377/Integration_of_migrants_in_Brussels_through_entrepreneurship_and_self-employment.pdf

²⁷ <https://www.nbg.gr/en/business/business-life-cycle/results-anaptiksi/female-entrepreneurship-useful-information>

²⁸ <https://sprintx.it/blog/finanziamenti-startup-femminile/#:~:text=Agevolazione%3A%20Finanziamenti%20variabili%20tra%20100.000,a%20fondo%20perduto%20del%2030%25.>

²⁹ <https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/rafforziamo-le-imprese/imprese-innovative-femminili-montane-ifim>

- Non-repayable contributions and subsidised financing for self-employment with majority or total participation of women or young people³⁰.
 - ON – Beyond New Zero-Rate Businesses, to support micro and small businesses composed mainly or entirely of young people under 35 or women of any age. It consists of a mix of non-repayable grants and interest-free loans to be used for the creation of new businesses, expansion or transformation of existing activities³¹.
 - New SELFIEmployment – for NEETs (young people aged 18-29 who are not in education, training or employment) to start small business initiatives³².
 - Youth Guaranty – self-entrepreneurship, business creation and development of entrepreneurial skills and the creation of self-employment or business activities by young people aged 18-35³³.
 - Futurae, Migrant Business Programme, promoted by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies and UNIONCAMERE “to support the development and consolidation of migrant entrepreneurship in order to promote inclusive growth, also in terms of opportunities for the creation of new jobs for foreign or Italian citizens³⁴”.
- *Norway*
- Zero Emissions Resource Organisation teaches young adults (25-35 years old) interdisciplinary knowledge about climate solutions and climate policy. Participants become part of a network of like-minded young people and meet mentors with extensive experience in climate management. Albeit this policy has not been specifically conceived for micro-entrepreneurs, it deserves to be mentioned, as there are a significant number of young people trying to set up micro-enterprises.
- *Romania*
- SIFE- Support (funded by the European commission) for the sustainable growth of micro-enterprises and job creation; funded actions should be promoted by a company in which at least 50% of the shareholders are women³⁵.
 - Fonduri Nerambursabile Pentru Femei – programmes dedicated exclusively to women entrepreneurs, giving them access to training, workshops and networking³⁶.

The above list is by no means exhaustive. However, it seems that Italy and Belgium give more attention to micro-enterprises run by disadvantaged people than the other three countries. Almost none of these schemes (with some notable exceptions in Italy) explicitly include measures to improve the environmental sustainability of micro-enterprises.

³⁰ <https://www.informazionefiscale.it/contributi-a-fondo-perduto-finanziamenti-agevolati-autoimprenditorialita-donne-giovani-decreto-mise>

³¹ <https://www.invitalia.it/cosa-facciamo/creiamo-nuove-aziende/nuove-imprese-a-tasso-zero/cose>

³² <https://giovani2030.it/iniziativa/selfiemployment/>

³³ <https://www.politichegiovani.gov.it/politiche-giovanili/attivita-internazionali/youthwiki/3-occupazione-e-imprenditoria/3-9-finanziamento-iniziale-per-giovani-imprenditori/>

³⁴ <https://www.integrazionemigranti.gov.it/it-it/Dettaglio-progetto/id/58/Futurae-Programma-Imprese-Migranti->

³⁵ Only in some territorial areas of Romania (Gorj, Hunedoara, Dolj, Galati, Prahova and Mureş) - <https://www.sife.ro/2024/01/26/sprijin-pentru-cresterea-durabila-a-microintreprinderilor-si-crearea-de-locuri-de-munca/>

³⁶ <https://www.neotrust.ro/fonduri-nerambursabile-pentru-femei/>

1.3.4 Vulnerability, marginalisation and disadvantage from a gender+ intersectional perspective reflected among the (groups of) study participants

The 21 case studies have been recruited based on the ACCTING gender+ intersectional perspective (see Table 1, below).

Table 1: Vulnerability grounds of the recruited micro-entrepreneurs per country

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	TOTAL
Gender	5	3	2	-	3	13
LGBTQ+ status	-	1	1	-	-	2
Migrant/Nationality	5	2	3	3	1	14
Social class	1	-	2	-	-	3
Language	-	-	-	3	1	4
Political discrimination	-	-	1	-	-	1
Religion/Ethnicity	2	-	-	-	-	2
Age	-	3	-	1	2	6
Geographic location	-	-	-	1	-	1
Other	1	-	-	-	-	1
Number of criteria assigned per number of interviewees	14/5	9/4	9/4	8/4	7/4	47/21

Under ‘gender’ are included all the women micro-entrepreneurs interviewed, even though some of them do not consider this to be a criterion of vulnerability. This choice is to some extent justified by the literature, which often stresses that women entrepreneurs face greater difficulties than their male counterparts (e.g. struggling to be taken seriously, accessing funding, and balancing business and family life)³⁷. They are therefore considered to be in a disadvantaged position, over and above their subjective assessment. It can also be added that almost all the women recruited (with one exception) are in any case people who can be considered vulnerable according to at least one other vulnerability criterion (e.g., migrant, LGBTQ+, political discrimination).

³⁷ Guzman, J., & Kacperczyk, A. O. (2019). Gender gap in entrepreneurship. *Research Policy*, 48(7), 1666-1680. Uzialko, A. (2023). Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneurs. Available at: <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/5268-women-entrepreneur-challenges.html>. Carranza, E., Dhakal, C., & Love, I. (2018). Female entrepreneurs: How and why are they different? Available at: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/400121542883319809/pdf/Female-Entrepreneurs-How-and-Why-are-They-Different.pdf>; Verheul, I., Stel, A. V., & Thurik, R. (2006). Explaining female and male entrepreneurship at the country level. *Entrepreneurship and regional development*, 18(2), 151-183. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/45132963_Explaining_Female_and_Male_Entrepreneurship_at_the_Country_Level.

Something similar can be said about the criterion 'age' (again with the support of some literature³⁸), under which five young micro-entrepreneurs were classified (in addition to one older entrepreneur, see 3.2.1).

Globally, the 21 micro-entrepreneurs are characterised by 47 vulnerability conditions, i.e., just over two per person. This ratio is quite similar in the five countries, but slightly higher in Belgium.

Going into the specific vulnerability grounds:

- 2 out of 3 micro-entrepreneurs involved are migrants
- Almost 2 out of 3 micro-entrepreneurs are women
- Almost 2 in 3 of the micro-entrepreneurs involved are vulnerable under the social class profile
- Almost 2 in 3 of the micro-entrepreneurs involved are vulnerable under the age profile (most are youth)
- 1 in 7 of the micro-entrepreneurs involved are subject to forms of political, ethnic and/or religious discrimination
- LGBTQ+ status, language and geographical location are the other vulnerability criteria considered.

1.3.5 Recruitment processes

As already mentioned (Section 1.3.2), in each country, four or five vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs were recruited (each of them possibly characterised by at least two vulnerability conditions). These entrepreneurs have embarked on a path towards environmental sustainability in their business, by adopting or at least designing measures in the field of energy transition or in other environmental areas.

In all five countries, we encountered many difficulties in recruitment due to the generally very low availability of micro-entrepreneurs to be interviewed (reluctance to talk about their own business, lack of time, mistrust, etc.). It was even more difficult to find available micro-entrepreneurs who were also vulnerable. The difficulties were compounded by the need to conduct three rounds of interviews with the same entrepreneur. In most cases, the assistance of mutually trusted intermediaries was required to complete the recruitment process. The intermediaries introduced the researchers and the ACCTING project to the micro-entrepreneurs prior to the first direct contact by the researcher, who only made contact once the micro-entrepreneurs had agreed to participate. The next section provides further details on that.

2. Methodology and study materials

2.1 General research design is put in practice and the choice of methods

³⁸ Yoganandan, G., & Vignesh, T. (2017). Challenges of young entrepreneurs. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research*, 1(56), 112-115. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344336561_CHALLENGES_OF_YOUNG_ENTREPRENEURS. Khan, S. J. M. (2020). *Youth Entrepreneurship in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)*. Talent Development for Youth Entrepreneurship (UUM Press), 101; Tessema, G. (2015). Assessing the challenges of youth entrepreneurship in micro and small-scale enterprises: the case of North Gondar zone, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(12), 53-64.

The entrepreneurs to be involved were identified following a screening of micro-enterprises run by vulnerable people in each of the five countries (or rather, in each selected territorial area in each country). This preliminary survey in these areas (and related countries) considered:

- The main characteristics of micro-enterprises in the area
- The existence of informal and formal networks between companies
- The existence and activities of any profit (e.g., ESCOs) and non-profit organisations (e.g., NGOs) assisting migrants (both in general and in relation to environmental issues)
- The availability (or not) of tools (funds, projects, policies/regulations) from which micro-enterprises can benefit to improve their environmental sustainability
- The presence and activities of pro-environmental citizens’ associations, including those dealing with the impact of business on the environment and/or working with businesses.

This preliminary research consisted mainly of desk review but also included the consultation of some experts (local authorities, business associations, trade unions, NGOs supporting entrepreneurs, consumer associations and environmental movements). During this consultation, the intermediaries who helped to recruit the 21 vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs were identified and consulted.

Each of the 21 selected micro-entrepreneurs corresponds to a case. Given the great heterogeneity of micro-enterprises, we have tried to concentrate on a few sectors of activity in order to ensure a degree of comparability between cases. However, this was not always possible due to the great difficulties encountered during the recruitment process (see above). The economic sectors of activity covered in each country are shown in Table 2 below (some micro-enterprises cover more than one economic activity, so the sum of the totals is greater than 21).

Table 2: Economic sectors covered by the micro-enterprises per country

Economic sectors of activity	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	TOTAL
Hotels/B&B	1	1	-	-	-	2
Food service (restaurant, bar, pub, bakery)	1	1	3	2	3	10
Culture (e.g., bookshop), environmental products, and leisure	1	-	1	1	1	4
Textile/fashion	2	-	1	-	-	3
Handcrafted products (including jewellery)	1	2	-	-	-	3
Retailers (e.g., plastic, electrical installations)	-	-	-	1	1	2

Almost all cases are located in urban/urbanised areas (with the exception of two cases in Norway). In urban areas, some of the selected entrepreneurs work in the suburbs, while others work in more central areas. A few of these micro-entrepreneurs, particularly those working in the textile sector, also have part of their business activities in third countries (such as India, Rwanda or Sierra Leone).

The fieldwork involved three rounds of interviews with each of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs over a period of 6/8 months, including visits to observe their environment and informal interviews with people working in the micro-enterprise, customers, etc.

The first round entailed an in-depth interview with the micro-entrepreneur on the following issues:

- Background of the micro-entrepreneurs (gender, age, living situation, vulnerability profile, family, education, attitude towards the environment, work experience and how they became a micro-entrepreneur, etc.)
- Main characteristics and history of the micro-enterprise (product/service, turnover, when it was founded, how it has developed and possible crises, etc.)
- Actors within the enterprise (employees, associates and, if relevant, their vulnerability profile)
- External actors, relations with them and possible benefits (clients, consultants, networks/cooperation arrangements, business associations, ESCOs, NGOs, local authorities, etc.)
- Imagined/planned/undertaken path towards environmental sustainability
- Motivations (what made you want to adopt more sustainable practices in your company? What made you want to change?)
- Satisfaction level (with the process of change implemented/planned)
- Opportunities/support encountered in moving towards environmental sustainability
- Obstacles/difficulties encountered on the way to environmental sustainability and how they have been/are being addressed
- Behavioural change (if any) of the micro-entrepreneur in the management of the micro-enterprise, in relation to environmental issues (compared to one or two years ago)
- Behavioural change (if any) of the micro-entrepreneur in everyday life, in relation to environmental issues (compared to one or two years ago)
- Behavioural change (if any) of the associates/employees, in relation to environmental issues (compared to one or two years ago)
- Perception of the adopted environmental sustainability measures by customers and other external actors.

The first round entailed also, as far as possible, the observation of the business (e.g., locations where the production of goods and/or the provision of service to clients is carried out, visible adopted measures) and informal talks with employees/associates and clients. A specific report has been done immediately after each visit.

Between the first and second rounds, an inventory was made of all the measures taken and planned for environmental sustainability, taking into account all 21 cases (see Table 3 below), and an attempt was made to identify, albeit in a somewhat rough way, those – adopted by others – that might be relevant to each micro-entrepreneur. Thus, the second round, which took place a few months after the first, consisted not only of updating the relevant points listed above, but mainly of a brainstorming session in which each micro-entrepreneur discussed possible relevant measures (for their business) adopted by other micro-entrepreneurs. During the brainstorming session, possible funding opportunities and other incentives that they might be able to access were also presented and

discussed, as well as actors (ESCOs, business associations, NGOs) with whom they could usefully get in touch. Here too, a specific report has been done immediately after each brainstorming session.

Table 3: Environmental measures adopted by the micro-entrepreneurs per country

Environmental measures adopted	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	TOTAL
Energy auditor	BE01					1
Insulation of floor, roof walls, façade	BE01					1
Solar/photovoltaic panel(s)	BE02				RO01	2
Efficient equipment for heating/air conditioning/refrigerators/boiler/geo-spreader		GR01 GR02	IT04	NO01	RO02 RO03	6
Efficient cooking methods			IT01 IT02			2
Changing light bulbs to LED		GR01 GR02 GR03	IT01		RO01 RO02 RO03 RO04	8
Power shuts down automatically (if not used) or equivalent		GR02	IT01 IT04			3
Reducing washing machine usage (includes offering customers the option not to change towels and sheets)		GR02	IT03			2
Waste sorting	BE02	GR03	IT01 IT02 IT04		RO02 RO04	7
No plastic packaging and only using sustainable cardboard boxes	BE02 BE05		IT02	NO03	RO02 RO04	6
Using wooden forks/knives, paper straws, only glass bottles		GR03	IT02 IT04	NO03 NO04		4
Waste recycling (including food and minimizing food waste)	BE05	GR02 GR03	IT01 IT02 IT04	NO02 NO03 NO04	RO02 RO03	11
Recycling textile waste	BE05		IT03			2
Reducing the use of water bottles		GR02	IT02 IT04			3
Climate calculator and fertiliser plans				NO01		1

Environmental measures adopted	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	TOTAL
Local purchasing policy for raw materials	BE03					
Using sustainable/eco-friendly products		GR01 GR02 GR03	IT02 IT04		RO04	6
Food ethics principles such as Fair Trade/Certified and 0km supply chain		GR02	IT02 IT04	NO04	RO03 RO04	6
Certifications for the materials used	BE05					1
Carefully selecting third-country producers/partners to work with in terms of social and environmental sustainability	BE05					1
Reducing transport carbon footprint (includes lower emissions from shipping by cargo ship rather than by air)	BE05	GR01	IT03			3
Using electric cars/electric bikes for delivery					RO01 RO02 RO03	3
'Slow fashion': artisanal handmade products that last for years and are not meant to be thrown away quickly			IT03			1
Daily cleaning of the park			IT02			1
Environmental sustainability awareness raising initiatives			IT04		RO02	2
Eco-feminist projects			IT04			1
Producing renewable plastic products				NO02		1

The third round consisted of a final interview with each micro-entrepreneur on the following issues:

- General changes since the second interview on the relevant items listed above for the first round (e.g., progress on environmental sustainability measures/practices made, in progress and started)
- Whether and how some of the issues discussed in the brainstorming session during the second visit have been taken up or are planned to be taken up
- Positive/negative consequences of the changes already implemented
- Expected future path towards greater environmental sustainability
 - Micro-entrepreneur level
 - Level of the associates/employees and clients

- Expected future development of the business
- Advice on policies that could support micro-enterprises in contributing to the ecological/environmental transition.

As done in the two previous rounds, there too, a specific report has been drafted after each visit.

From what has been described so far, it should be clear that the practical implementation of the research design has been refined progressively, thanks to careful monitoring of the progress of this second research cycle and taking advantage of the numerous meetings between the partners involved in RL4.

This has allowed the research team to conceptualise what is considered to be a green micro-enterprise, which made it possible to assign a positive or negative outcome to the 21 cases analysed. We are dealing with a green micro-enterprise when:

- Environmental sustainability is high on the company's agenda
- Significant investments/expenditures (meaning an expenditure that is not routine, but needs to be planned; which necessitates the foregoing or procrastination of other expenses; and which is then stretched over time; and all if this, according to the dimension of the business) have been made in environmental sustainability (relative to the size and purpose of the business)
- An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted (e.g., measures in several areas)
- Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process
- There is confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken
- There is a positive propensity to:
 - consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises
 - consider subsidies/incentives they may be eligible for and/or calls for proposals or other opportunities that may be useful in moving towards environmental sustainability
 - consider ESCOs, networks or other actors to which the entrepreneur could usefully turn in order to progress in the path towards environmental sustainability.

Of course, not all the eight criteria listed above (further referred to as 'outcome determinants') need to be met for a positive outcome to occur. But at least most of them must be (in full or in part).

The following algorithm has been adopted. For each of the eight determinants, we assigned:

- a score = 2 if positive
- a score = 1 if partial/weak
- a score = 0 if negative.

Based on our knowledge of the real situation and previous studies in this regard, we do not believe that it is possible to establish a 'weighting' system between these eight factors with sufficient justification. It could be assumed, for example, that the factor 'Significant investments/expenditures' should be much more important than the others; but this is not necessarily true since sometimes even significant investments are made for purely economic reasons (for their economic return or to take advantage of an incentive). Or one might consider 'Environmental sustainability is high on the company's agenda' to be of greater importance. But this could be so without practical consequences

due to emergency situations or the daily routine. Likewise, an ‘integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted’ is very important, but it could be backed up by actions in multiple areas (from energy efficiency to waste management), all of which are of very little importance. The same could be applied to ‘Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process’ (with attention to diachrony instead of synchrony). Thus, considering that a weighing system could not be reasonably justified, all factors are given an equal weight (=1)³⁹.

Consequently, the scores for each micro-entrepreneurs according to the eight determinants were simply added up. As there are eight determinants, this sum can vary from 0 to 16. If the total score is >10⁴⁰, the result (i.e., from 11 onwards) is associated with a positive outcome. Otherwise, it is associated with a negative outcome.

Our research design also involved a synthetic *prima facie* assessment by each national research team, considering the individual country cases.

Last but not least, it should be specified that RL4 in the second research cycle included action research components, in the sense that the progressive results and the way the research was implemented may have (not accidentally, but intentionally) influenced behavioural changes towards environmental sustainability among the interviewed micro-entrepreneurs (Hawthorne effect⁴¹). This was particularly the case through the brainstorming⁴² carried out during the second round and the evaluation of its impact during the third round.

2.2 The study material used for data collection (and measurements of relevant variables)

All interviews were conducted using semi-structured grids. These were more structured in the first and third rounds and less so in the second, as the content of the brainstorming sessions was tailored to each micro-entrepreneur. Only the first-round grid was designed at the beginning of the process, while the second and third were designed later, on the basis of the results that were gradually obtained. The interview reporting template (corresponding to the case study reporting template), summarising the findings from the three rounds of interviews, was drafted at the end of the process. Finally, the country report template was drafted by each national team.

All information and data were collected in a harmonised way across the five countries and 21 cases, as the methodological approach and technical tools were the same (with the exception of the brainstorming tools in the second round, which were tailored to each micro-entrepreneur, based on

³⁹ In the construction of most composite indicators, the same weight is attributed to the elementary indicators when the theoretical structure does not allow for the consistent derivation of hypotheses for differentiating weights (and also when there is no agreement on adoptable alternatives or insufficient statistical or empirical knowledge on which to base the definition of weights; and - of course - also when the theoretical structure underlying the construction of the composite indicator attributes to each of the elementary indicators the same sufficiency in defining the composite concept to be measured). See: Maggino F. (2004). I modelli di scaling. Confronto tra ipotesi complesse per la misurazione del soggettivo (*Scaling models. Comparison of complex hypotheses for measuring the subjective*), Firenze University Press, Archivio E-Prints, Firenze.

⁴⁰ Higher than ten means at least equal to eleven, the value corresponding to the second tercile. To obtain at least this moderately high value, a positive assessment is required for at least 3 criteria and a negative assessment is not possible for more than 2 criteria.

⁴¹ The Hawthorne effect is the modification of behaviour by study participants in response to their knowledge that they are being observed or singled out for special treatment. In the simpler terms, the Hawthorne effect is increasing output in response to being watched. See: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchhrsoftware/definition/Hawthorne-effect>

⁴² Through these brainstorming sessions we can say that ACCTING contributed to the introduction/reinforcement of knowledge pluralisation practices in the field of energy efficiency/environmental sustainability. This could be considered as a specific impact of this RL. Another specific impact facilitated by the brainstorming sessions is the replicability of impact, as they aimed to facilitate the replication of environmental sustainability measures in other micro enterprises.

the specific features of her/his specific business; as mentioned in Section 2.1 each entrepreneur was presented with potential innovative measures or incentives relevant to her/his own specific business). However, as these are semi-structured grids used with very different micro-enterprises by different researchers from different countries, there remains a certain degree of potential divergences in operation. To mitigate this problem, the grids were analysed in great detail by the researchers in the different teams, and any doubts were discussed and clarifications agreed. The same was done in the design of the final interview report template.

As mentioned above, 13 of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs involved are women. In fact, an attempt was made, within reasonable limits, to give considerable weight to the experience of women micro-entrepreneurs, both in recruitment and in the analysis. An environmentally active feminist micro-enterprise was also included in the sample. In addition, attention was paid to gender differences and potential discrimination when interviewing women micro-entrepreneurs.

Research participants were provided with a consent form which included information about the project, the purpose of the research, the research design and what would happen to the data collected. Participating entrepreneurs gave their informed consent by signing these forms. In the majority of cases, participants were first approached by a trusted partner (i.e., the business association contacted by the researchers or other intermediaries such as migrant networks) and asked whether they would be interested in participating in the research. Interested parties were then put in touch with the researchers and given the opportunity to ask for further information before participating in the research.

As seen above, a qualitative RL design has been adopted, which does not involve the measurement of any variables (beyond simple counts). As for the modalities of outcome assessment, these have already been specified above (score for each of the outcome determinants).

All the completed grids related to the three rounds of interviews and the completed interview report template for each of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs are stored in the ACCTING SharePoint and are thus accessible to the five country research teams.

Analysis and Results

3. Data collected and analysis

3.1 Steps and timeframe of data collection

The data collection started, as already mentioned, with documentary research (from June to September 2023) and continued with fieldwork, which included three rounds of interviews. Due to the aforementioned difficulties in recruitment, the first round was the longer one, starting in October 2023 with the first interviews (coupled with visits to the enterprises) with a few micro-entrepreneurs and ending at the end of January 2024. After a first rough analysis of the results of the first round, the second round started at the end of February 2024 and lasted until mid-May (but with a few extensions in the following weeks). The third round started at the end of May and lasted until mid-July 2024.

The data collection took place in parallel in the five countries. Within these periods, however, there were some discrepancies between the 21 cases, with some micro-entrepreneurs being interviewed at the beginning of a period and others at the end. Overall, this meant that between the first and the last interview of each micro-entrepreneur there was a minimum of six months and a maximum of eight months.

3.2 Overview of the sample statistic(s) of participants in the RL4 case studies

3.2.1 Micro-entrepreneurs

The types of vulnerability, marginalisation and disadvantage from a gender+ intersectional perspective that characterise the 21 case studies have already been presented above (Section 1.3). As we saw then, most of the vulnerability profiles (also often in an intersectional way) are represented in the sample of 21 cases. The only exception is 'disability'.

Gender. As noted above, most of the micro-entrepreneurs involved (13 out of 21) are women. Among them, two have identified themselves as LGBTQIA+.

Age. Most of the micro-entrepreneurs involved (14 out of 21) are between 37 and 45 years old. There are six younger micro-entrepreneurs (between 24 and 30 years old) and an older one (63 years old).

Educational degree. The educational level of most of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs involved in the research is high. 15 out of 21 have a university degree. This can be explained by the fact that some of them are migrants who came to Europe to study and then became micro-entrepreneurs. Four have secondary or professional qualifications, one has primary education, and one of the interviewees never went to school. In one case the educational level is not known.

Migrant. As noted above, most of the micro-entrepreneurs involved (14 out of 21) are migrant. Migrant entrepreneurs in all five countries were interviewed.

Voluntary work in environmental NGOs and/or participation in ecological movement activities. Environmental volunteering is only practised by six micro-entrepreneurs. It can be within an ecological movement (e.g., IT04, woman; NO04, man) or a migrant association (e.g., GR04 and IT03, both women).

Employment status. All the 21 micro-entrepreneurs are employed full-time. Behind this uniform façade, however, there are very different realities. In four cases, the micro-entrepreneur benefits from a full-time job somewhere outside the micro-enterprise and earns nothing or almost nothing in the micro-enterprise. In the other cases, they work for their micro-enterprise, sometimes with a normal employment contract; in other cases, their income, if any, depends on the results of the business.

3.2.2 Micro-enterprises

Turning now to the 21 enterprises managed by the participating micro-entrepreneurs, the sectors of activity have already been presented above (see Section 2.1). Some additional information can be provided.

Juridical status of the business. Eleven enterprises are sole proprietorships and seven are limited liability companies. This difference is not very important, as it depends mainly on the national rules for setting up companies in the different countries. Much more important is the fact that in three cases (one in Italy, one in Belgium and one in Norway) we are dealing with informal micro-enterprises, i.e., enterprises which (at least until the last round) were not legally constituted. These are therefore particularly weak actors.

Turnover. The amount of turnover was only reported in 13 of the 21 cases, and often only approximately. It is very variable: in four cases (three in Belgium and one in Italy) it is less than 30,000 Euros per year (including the three informal enterprises), in another four cases (one in Belgium, two in Italy and one in Romania) between 60,000 and 130,000 Euros, in two cases (both in Norway) between 170,000 and 200,000 Euros and in the remaining three cases (one in Italy, one in Norway and one in Romania) more than 300,000 Euros.

Employees/associates. In 10 out of 21 cases (including all informal enterprises) the entrepreneur works alone or with one other person (often on a part-time basis; in some cases, a family member) and in other cases with two or three people. In other cases, there is a larger number of employees/associates, up to a maximum of ten.

3.2.3 Comparability

Each of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs is a case in itself and, of course, the four or five vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs involved in RL4 in each country (and even more the 21 as a whole at European level) represent only a qualitative sample of the different paths that vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs can take to improve the environmental sustainability of their business. We are therefore less interested in comparability between countries than in looking at all the country cases together (as a whole).

3.3 Results of the individual case studies and the country studies

All the micro-entrepreneurs recruited are at least minimally on a path towards environmental sustainability (which was a selection criterion). However, **only for 15 of them can the outcome be considered positive** as defined in the research design (sum of the scores of the right determinants > 10, see Section 2.1).

The subsequent section looks in detail at the situation of the 21 cases, taking into account all the determinants of the outcome. They are presented below (see Tables 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8), country by country.

3.3.1 Basic analysis of cases

Belgium

Table 4: Determinants of the outcome – Belgium

	BE01	BE02	BE03	BE04	BE05
Environmental sustainability is high on the company’s agenda	Yes	Partially	Partially	No	Partially
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	Partially	Yes	No	No	Partially
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	Yes	Yes	No	No	Partially
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	Yes	Yes	Low	No	Yes
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	Yes	No	Low	Partially	Partially
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	Yes	Partially	No	Partially	Low
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	Yes	Partially	Low	Partially	Partially
SCORE	15	11	4	3	8
SYNTHESIS OUTCOME	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	NEGATIVE	NEGATIVE

It should be noted that in two of the three cases where the result is considered negative, this result is clear. These are all cases where the micro-entrepreneur has the best intentions (sometimes thanks to the input from ACCTING), but where almost nothing or very little has been done, even at the time of the third round, and the propensity to consider concrete instruments for change is limited. These cases are:

- BE03, a Belgian woman of North-African origin, aged around 40, with a degree in education, who runs a jewellery business and a shop where local entrepreneurs can sell their products (around 30 suppliers).
- BE04, a Belgian woman of around 40 years of age, originally from West Africa, with part of her family in East-Africa and with a professional qualification; she runs an artisanal fashion business, selling products such as bags, fashion accessories and some types of clothing (with a very low turnover) and working with people in East-Africa.

The two positive cases are very different. Specifically, in BE01 all result components are positive, while in BE02 many things have already been done (including significant investments) not just once and looking at multiple aspects. However, there is (so far) limited willingness to continue. These two cases are:

- BE01, a black American woman of around 40 years of age residing in Belgium and having a university degree in environmental issues; she manages an eco-friendly guesthouse with bed-and-breakfast amenities for travellers who stay overnight as well as a communal space on the ground floor that can host all kinds of events.
- BE02, a Belgian woman of around 40 years of age, who was born and raised in a Latin-American country and moved to Belgium fifteen years ago, with a higher education degree as a food technologist and several years of experience in the food industry; she manages a food production business, delivering and catering to professional clients (B2B).

The last case was assessed as negative based on the score and the subjective assessment of the Belgian team. However, some environmentally sustainable measures have been taken, although mostly on a one-off basis, and there is also an intention to make further progress, although this is limited. This case, BE05, corresponds to an Asian woman, of around 35 years of age in Belgium, with a university degree in law and coming from a family of entrepreneurs; she runs a business (with a very small turnover) selling textile products designed by her and produced by her business partners in India.

Greece

Table 5: Determinants of the outcome – Greece

	GR01	GR02	GR03	GR04
Environmental sustainability is high on the company’s agenda	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	No	Yes	Partially	No
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	Low	Yes	Yes	Low
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	Yes	Low	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	Partially	Yes	Yes	Low
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	Yes	Yes	Partially	Partially
SCORE	11	15	13	8
SYNTHESIS OUTCOME	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE

In Greece, 3 out of 4 cases have a positive outcome. Almost all outcome components are positive, leading the Greek team to give an overall positive outcome rating (confirmed by the score calculation). These cases are:

- GR01, a Greek woman, LGBTQ+, around 25 years of age, with a secondary education; she produces seasonal and everyday handmade decorations and souvenirs from wood and sells them wholesale all over Greece.
- GR02, a Greek man, of around 25 years of age, second-generation migrant with a university degree; he renovated a building and created a boutique hotel with ten rooms; this is his fourth season; he works there every year from the end of April to the end of October.
- GR03, woman, of around 40 years of age, with a secondary education; she came to Greece from Albania in 2008 in search of a better job and more opportunities; she runs a bakery that produces all the classic bakery products, from bread and bread sticks to small breakfast items such as cakes. She also makes some traditional Albanian pastries.

A negative outcome was assigned to GR04 (woman), a young Greek entrepreneur (around 25 years of age) with a university degree, who produces organic candles, delivers them and promotes them on social media. Again, this is not a clear-cut assessment (see table above). In this case, it is justified by the fact that the interviewee seemed to be much more concerned with everyday struggles and less with implementing sustainability measures.

Italy

Table 6: Determinants of the outcome – Italy

	IT01	IT02	IT03	IT04
Environmental sustainability is high on the company’s agenda	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	No	No	No	Partially
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	Partially	Yes	Yes	Yes
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	Partially	Low	Low	Yes
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	Low	Low	Low	Yes,
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	No	Low	Yes	Yes
SCORE	8	11	12	15

	IT01	IT02	IT03	IT04
SYNTHESIS OUTCOME	NEGATIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE

In Italy, 3 out of 4 cases have a positive result. One (IT04) is clearly positive in all outcome components. In the other two positive cases, most of the outcome components are positive, leading the team to give them an overall positive outcome rating. These cases are:

- IT02, man, a regular migrant from West-Africa, of around 40 years of age, arrived in Italy 25 years ago (as a farm worker), having no educational background; he manages, with an Italian associate, a restaurant and bar located in a medium-sized park; its business also assures the daily-maintenance of the park on behalf of the Municipality of Rome.
- IT03, woman, second-generation Italian with a migration background from West Africa, of around 30 years old, university graduate; she and her associate (also of migrant background) run a textile company that markets in Italy garments produced in West Africa in an artisanal way, also taking into account Italian fashion models; she also markets products of the migrant diaspora; the company has a very small turnover.
- IT04, woman, of around 40 years of age (who feels discriminated against as a lesbian), university graduate and dual Italian-French citizen (she is also of African descent); she runs (with five other people) a café that sells drinks, snacks, books and sex toys, and organises workshops on ecological issues and book launches on important topics.

A negative outcome was assigned to IT01. It is not an unequivocal assessment – see table above – but it is justified by the interviewee’s lack of substantial motivation towards environmental issues, as he adopted eco-sustainable measures almost exclusively for economic reasons. He is a man, a regular migrant, who came to Rome from Central-Africa more than 20 years ago to obtain a university degree and then to work in the catering sector; together with his sister, he runs a restaurant in Rome offering dishes from West and Central African cuisine.

Norway

Table 7: Determinants of the outcome – Norway

	NO01	NO02	NO03	NO04
Environmental sustainability is high on the company's agenda	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	Partially	Yes	No	Yes
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	No	Partially	Partially	Partially
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	Partially	Partially	Yes	No
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	No	Partially	Partially	No
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	Partially	Partially	Partially	Yes
SCORE	7	12	11	11
SYNTHESIS OUTCOME	NEGATIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE

Even in Norway, 3 out of 4 cases are associated with a positive outcome. These cases are:

- NO02, a French man of around 40 years of age with a background in engineering; he is concerned about the environment and climate change and his values have led him to create a business focused on recycling the plastic he buys as waste and turning it into a wide range of plastic items such as medals for sporting events.
- NO03, an immigrant from Middle-East [of around 40 years of age](#); he runs a small organic shop selling groceries such as flour, cereals, nuts, detergents and various other products.
- NO04, a man from Scotland of around 50 years of age; he runs a small café next to a farm that grows vegetables such as potatoes, carrots and the like. The café sells food and drink made from local produce or products that are ecologically and environmentally sustainable.

A fourth case is associated with a negative outcome. This is NO01, a Norwegian of around 65 years of age who runs a small dairy farm in a small village in northern Norway, producing milk and meat.

Romania

Table 8: Determinants of the outcome – Romania

	RO01	RO02	RO03	RO04
Environmental sustainability is high on the company's agenda	Yes	Yes	Partially	Yes
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	Yes	Yes	Yes	Partially
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	Yes	Low	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	Yes	Low	Yes	Yes
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	Yes	Partially	Yes	Partially
SCORE	16	13	15	14
SYNTHESIS OUTCOME	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE	POSITIVE

This is the only one of the five countries involved in RL4 where the outcomes of all the cases considered were assessed as positive. Moreover, this is unequivocal, since in none of the four cases was there even a negative rating for any of the outcome components. The cases are:

- RO01, a Romanian woman of around 40 years of age living on the outskirts of Iași, with a university degree, who has worked in the private sector in various positions; she now runs a company with her husband that offers electrical installations, electrical connections/ branching, electrical installation testing and inspection, energy audits and photovoltaic installation.
- RO02, a Romanian man, of around 25 years of age, with a bachelor's degree and currently enrolled in a master's degree in advanced processing systems and quality control of agri-food products; he runs a high-quality bakery selling artisan chocolates and sweets.
- RO03, a Romanian woman, of around 40 years of age, with a university degree; she has a food business producing bakery, pastry, traditional food, pizza, all to go (with a small turnover).
- RO04, a woman, of around 25 years of age, migrant from the Republic of Moldavia, who moved to Iași in 2018; she manages a restaurant serving traditional Moldavian (mainly from the Republic of Moldavia) dishes.

Cross-cutting analysis among countries

As can be seen in the tables above, the positive outcome (a micro-enterprise that designed/conceived measures for environmental sustainability and can be considered a green micro-enterprise) is defined in relation to eight determinants. These are present to a varying degree in the experience of the 21 entrepreneurs, as shown in the table below.

Table 9: Presence and intensity of the determinants of outcome in the 21 cases, by country

	Positive (Yes)	Partially	Low (No)
Environmental sustainability is high on the company's agenda	BE: 1 IT: 3 GR: 3 NO: 3 RO: 3 Tot: 13	BE: 3 IT: 1 GR: 1 NO: 1 RO: 1 Tot: 7	BE: 1 Tot: 1
Significant investments/expenditures have been made in environmental sustainability	BE: 1 GR: 1 NO: 2 RO: 3 Tot: 7	BE: 2 IT: 1 GR: 1 NO: 1 RO: 1 Tot: 6	BE: 2 IT: 3 GR: 2 NO: 1 Tot: 8
An integrated/multiple approach to environmental sustainability has been adopted	BE: 2 IT: 3 GR: 4 RO: 4 Tot: 13	BE: 1 IT: 1 NO: 3 Tot: 5	BE: 2 NO: 1 Tot: 3
Environmental actions are not one-off, but an ongoing or established process	BE: 2 IT: 4 GR: 4 NO: 4 RO: 4 Tot: 18	NA Tot: 0	BE: 3 Tot: 3
Confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken	BE: 3 IT: 4 GR: 2 NO: 4 RO: 4 Tot: 17	BE: 1 GR: 2 Tot: 3	BE: 1 Tot: 1

	Positive (Yes)	Partially	Low (No)
Propensity to consider relevant (environmental) measures/actions taken by other micro-enterprises	BE: 1	BE: 3	BE: 1
	IT: 1	IT: 3	NO: 1
	GR: 3	GR:1	
	NO: 1	NO: 2	
	RO: 3	RI:1	
	Tot: 9	Tot: 10	Tot: 2
Propensity to consider subsidies/incentives or other opportunities useful in moving towards environmental sustainability	BE: 1	BE: 3	BE: 1
	IT: 1	GR: 2	NO: 2
	GR: 2	IT:3	
	RO: 3	NO: 2	
		RO:1	
	Tot: 7	Tot: 11	Tot: 3
Propensity to consider ESCOs, networks or other actors in order to progress on the path towards environmental sustainability	BE: 1	BE: 4	IT: 1
	IT: 2	GR: 2	
	GR: 2	IT:1	
	NO:1	RO: 2	
	RO: 2	NO: 3	
	Tot: 8	Tot: 12	Tot: 1

Looking at the 21 cases covered by RL4 as a whole, it seems clear that some measures are easier for micro-entrepreneurs to adopt on their journey towards environmental sustainability, and others are less easy (or much less so). Below are some details about the different components of the outcome.

- i) As might be expected, many micro-enterprises find it difficult to make significant **investments/expenditures for environmental sustainability**, relatively speaking, given the size and purpose of the enterprise. However, this is not only due to a lack of funds and incentives/subsidies (whether non-existent or unknown to micro-entrepreneurs). It is also because such investments are either impossible (as in a case in Rome – IT02 – where the possible installation of a photovoltaic system was prohibited due to landscape constraints) or too complicated (IT01 – because the business is in a condominium and would need everyone’s consent, or because the premises are rented and the owner does not agree and/or does not want to contribute).
- ii) Conversely, almost all micro-entrepreneurs have **environmental sustainability very high on their agenda**. This was somewhat to be expected, as they were selected on the assumption that they had at least started (or at least planned/conceived) something to improve the environmental sustainability of their business. Indeed, in 13 cases this was and still is the case, while in seven others the concern for environmental sustainability is present but marginal and may have been reinforced by the contact with ACCTING. Only in one case (BE04), while the entrepreneur has values that would lead her to make the business more sustainable, she has not taken any decisions yet that could have a positive impact on the environment. Her current

focus is on increasing sales, and she does not seem to be taking the initiative on environmental measures.

- iii) This is almost always reflected in the trend to consider **environmental measures not as one-off, but as an ongoing or established process**. There are however four exceptions: the entrepreneur mentioned in the previous point and two others from Belgium (BE03 and BE05), plus an entrepreneur from Greece (GR04).
- iv) Entrepreneurs who have the environment very high on their agenda and see the adoption of measures as an ongoing process (rather than a one-off) tend to be highly confident in the **sustainability of the measures adopted**⁴³. There are two exceptions:
 - GR01 (woman), since she has no confidence in the future of her business because, as she states “The costs are going up daily and we struggle to keep our prices at a reasonable level. We also sell goods that are not of first need for somebody, like food or clothing.”
 - GR04 (woman), who seems much more worried about everyday struggles (financial issues which could jeopardise her business) than about implementing sustainability measures right now.
- v) The possible measures taken (as well as those still being planned or conceived) are quite heterogeneous (see the relevant table in Section 2.1, which presents the measures already taken/planned at the time of the first round) and cover several issues (energy efficiency, use of renewable energy, energy control, waste sorting, recycling, sustainable packaging and use of sustainable products, food ethics practices, sustainable mobility, raising people’s awareness of environmental sustainability, etc.). In this respect, 12 of the 21 participating micro-entrepreneurs have an **integrated/multiple approach** to environmental sustainability, i.e., they implement and plan measures related to all issues relevant to their business. The others have less or much less of this integrated approach, or none at all. The latter are people who act on the basis of specific inputs that are not dictated by a holistic vision of environmental sustainability. Some examples are shown below.
 - IT01 (man) adopted many measures (e.g., recycling and waste management methods; largely packaging-free catering: no plastic packaging and only sustainable cardboard boxes) and also actions to increase energy efficiency (e.g., rationalisation of energy use in cooking; rationalisation of the use of heating and air conditioning, changing light bulbs to LED). But it is in opposition towards any heavy measure his restaurant would need (changes of equipment, adoption of renewable energy, since the restaurant is in rented premises).
 - BE05 (woman) adopted some measures to achieve environmental sustainability (i.e., recycling, water conservation, and energy efficiency to an extent), but has not been able, until now, to consider other aspects.

Micro-enterprises that adopt an integrated or multiple approach to environmental sustainability should also have a multidimensional territorial impact, reducing the direct negative impact of the micro-enterprise in the area, both in terms of emissions of CO₂ and/or other gases and in terms of waste pollution and sanitation. We are not able to calculate or even estimate the size of these impacts, which are however likely to be non-negligible.

⁴³ This appears as a possible positive indicator of “Impact sustainability” of most of the 21 micro-enterprises involved in RL4-RC2.

vi) Most micro-entrepreneurs tend to mind their own business and therefore some are rather reluctant to enter into **new relationships and participate in networks with other entrepreneurs** in which they often have little trust. Some simply do not want to hear about it because they do not consider it a priority (IT02) or because they are not interested (IT01). In other cases (NO02 and NO04) there may also be some language barriers (both are migrants). In some other cases, the micro-entrepreneurs are members of associations or networks in their country (working, among other things, on environmental issues), or have established relations with such bodies with the help of ACCTING (e.g., IT03; BE04; GR02; RO02; RO04), but nothing concrete or almost nothing has happened in this respect by the end of the third round. Some examples are shown below.

- GR02 (man) is aware of the existence of “Green Labels”, which also extend to a network of sustainable enterprises. After ACCTING provided him with information on how to reach such networks, he said he was going to look at it. However, in the third interview, he mentioned that he did not proceed with it.
- RO02 (man) declared a similar interest in the second round without doing anything later, due to a lack of time and having other priorities.

On the other hand, there are cases of strongly structured relationships, such as:

- IT04 (woman) has stable relations with an Italian non-profit organisation that promotes energy transition and green awareness, and they organise ecological events together.
- BE01 (woman) had started an informal social club around environmental values, and she would invite people from her network and social club to organise events.

Relationships between entrepreneurs about environmental sustainability are relatively poor, with a few exceptions. Some examples are shown below.

- GR04 (woman) mentioned that she has some relationships with other small businesses that also make or distribute sustainable products, like soaps and sponges for the bath.
- Finally, it is worth mentioning the case of two women entrepreneurs (IT03 and BE04, both women), who trade in textile products manufactured in Africa (both in close relation with textile laboratories in Africa). They face very similar problems and have both expressed a strong interest in dialogue with each other. ACCTING has therefore put them in contact. However, a concrete contact between the two of them has not yet taken place.

vii) As might be expected, almost all micro-entrepreneurs who have environmental issues high on their agenda express an **interest in incentives and subsidies** or other ways of improving their environmental sustainability. In one case (IT02), the business was set up in response to a call for proposals from the Municipality of Rome (to renovate a restaurant in a park in Rome in harmony with nature and to ensure the maintenance of the park). There are cases where the entrepreneur has very clear and specific ideas on the subject (e.g., BE01 is interested in the subsidy for the purchase of a bicycle trailer for ‘cyclologic’ activities, since she does not use a car), while sometimes (e.g., IT04) it is commonplace to look for all opportunities and in particular to respond to relevant calls for proposals. Other entrepreneurs, on the other hand, were much less familiar with the issue and took action/are taking action based on the input from ACCTING (e.g., GR01 found out about the proposed opportunity for a photovoltaic and asked for an offer between the second and third round; GR02 found out that replacing old refrigerators can be eligible in a call). In some cases, however, the micro-entrepreneurs’ willingness to do so is

low/partial due to a lack of confidence in obtaining such funding (e.g., IT01). In other cases, the entrepreneurs have to take into account the low relevance of such opportunities for their business (e.g., IT01, BE04, GR04, RO01, RO02, and RO04). Still, some entrepreneurs stated that they did not have the time to look for such opportunities (BE03), while others (BE02) seemed interested in some of the suggestions and made notes during the second round, but they did not yet have the time to look into them further. In some cases, no action was taken (NO01, NO04,), or only a few (NO02), due to a mix of lack of money, time and the need to get back to work.

- viii) The reactions of the entrepreneurs to suggestions on measures for environmental sustainability coming from the **experiences of other entrepreneurs** are very different. In two cases, the entrepreneurs feel that they are already “at the top” (but both are open to further suggestions):
- RO02 (man): the enterprise already adopted several sustainable practices that required significant investment, in multiple fields, and there are plans to move forward in the same direction.
 - GR02 (man): The hotel is already ‘green’ as it has implemented sustainability measures for almost everything in its daily operations.

In other cases, it was noted that the suggested measures are already practised in their own business (e.g., IT01, IT02, BE02, RO01).

Most of the other entrepreneurs are also open, at least apparently, to suggestions coming (through ACCTING) from other people interviewed. And sometimes also substantially:

- BE05 (woman): although she is limited by the fact that she is renting the building for the store, she was very interested in installing better heating and would discuss this hypothesis with the architect she hired.
- GR04 (woman): when mentioning recycle bins for different materials, especially glass, that can then be brought to specialised recycle stations and receive a small amount of money for them, she found it a really good, easy, and practical idea and mentioned that she will definitely proceed with it.
- BE04 (woman): the same when sustainable packaging and sustainable supply chains were mentioned.

In other cases, entrepreneurs are open, but they raise multiple problems, such as:

- The lack of budget (e.g., GR04): the interviewee said she has a very low budget to provide for future changes towards sustainability despite her good intentions.
- The limited relevance: when the insulation on the windows and walls to reduce the energy loss was suggested, she was hesitant and mentioned that the shop is relatively small and has low levels of energy loss due to insulation (GR03, woman); he hesitates to renew the cooking equipment, since it is rented and risks, if it changes premises, not benefiting from the investment that would be made (IT01 man).

3.3.2 Advanced analysis (Outcome analysis)

Outcome and vulnerability profile of the micro-entrepreneurs

As mentioned above, the outcome of the 21 analysed cases was assessed to be positive in 15 cases and negative in the remaining six. The ratio between positive and negative outcomes is, therefore, five to seven (positive cases) and two to seven (negative cases).

Let’s now have a look at how this data is distributed across the different vulnerability criteria (note that almost all respondents are classified under more than one type of vulnerability).

Table 10: Outcome by vulnerability factor

	Positive	Negative	Total
Gender	BE01; BE02; GR01; GR03; IT03; IT04; RO01; RO03; RO04 Tot: 9	BE03; BE04; BE05; GR04 Tot: 4	Tot:13
LGBTQIA+ status	IT04; GR01 Tot: 2	Tot: 0	Tot: 2
Migrant/Nationality	BE01; BE02; GR02; GR03; IT02; IT03; NO02; NO03; NO04; RO04 Tot: 10	BE03; BE04; BE05; IT01 Tot: 4	Tot: 14
Social class	BE01; IT02 Tot: 2	IT01 Tot: 1	Tot: 3
Language	NO02, NO04; RO04 Tot: 3	NO01 Tot: 1	Tot: 4
Political/Religious discrimination	BE01 Tot: 1	BE03; IT03 Tot: 2	Tot: 3
Age	GR01; GR02; RO02; RO04 Tot: 4	GR04; NO01 Tot: 2	Tot: 6
Geographic location	NO04 Tot: 1	Tot: 0	Tot: 1
Other	Tot: 0	BE03 Tot: 1	Tot: 1
TOTAL	15	6	21

In relation to almost all vulnerability criteria, the five/seven to two/seven ratio between positive and negative outcomes is almost perfectly respected:

- Gender 9 versus 4
- Migrant/nationality 10 versus 4

- Age 4 versus 2

The ratio is also almost perfectly respected for the social class criterion (2 to 1), but the numbers are too small to say anything; and this is also the case for all the other criteria where the ratio is not respected. So, as far as the small number of 21 cases is concerned, it seems that the vulnerability profile (in particular gender, age and migrant status) has no influence.

However, this is not to say that vulnerability profiles do not have an impact on the outcome. Looking in more detail, it appears that:

- Women are more interested than men in putting into practice (or at least considering concretely) measures (towards environmental sustainability) suggested by other entrepreneurs; men are more often only seemingly open (often thinking that they have already done or already know what needs to be done in their business).
- Similarly, beyond the talk, women are more concretely interested than men in incentives, subsidies and other opportunities.
- The cases of real and effective openness towards external parties are all of female entrepreneurs.
- Conversely, the only two cases of lack of confidence in the sustainability of the measures taken (indeed in the sustainability of their business) are also women micro-entrepreneurs.

Outcome and educational level of the micro-entrepreneurs

Data on the level of education of the micro-entrepreneurs were already presented above (Section 3.3). In the table below, these data are crossed with the assessment of the outcome (codes in bold refer to cases with a positive outcome).

Contrary to what might be expected, there is no strong (or clear) relationship between the level of education and the positive or negative outcomes in that the ‘sample’ is very unbalanced towards individuals with a university degree, but on the other hand it also turns out that a low level of education is not necessarily an impediment to a positive outcome, as the case of IT02 shows (IT02, an irregular migrant who came to Italy to pick tomatoes, working twelve hours a day, now president of an agricultural cooperative and co-owner of a restaurant in a park in Rome, after winning a call for proposals from the Municipality of Rome).

Table 11: Outcome by educational level

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
No education at all			IT02			1 (1)
Elementary degree				NO01		1 (0)
Secondary/Professional degree	BE03 BE04	GR01 GR03				4 (2)
University degree	BE01 BE02 BE05	GR02 GR04	IT01 IT03 IT04	NO02 NO03 NO04	RO01 RO02 RO03 RO04	15 (12)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

Outcome and business turnover

We have already presented data above on the turnover of the micro-enterprises (unfortunately only available in 13 cases, see Section 3.3). In the table below, these data are cross-referenced with the assessment of the outcome and, again, the codes in bold refer to the cases that had a positive outcome. Even if we consider that we are dealing with a very small number of cases, we cannot fail to notice a clear difficulty for those micro-enterprises which are truly microscopic in terms of their turnover (and which, moreover, largely coincide with the “informal” ones, i.e., those not legally constituted as enterprises). Nevertheless, one of them did achieve a positive result, as did 3 out of 4 of those with a small budget.

Otherwise, there seems to be no other relationship between the turnover of micro-enterprises and the positivity or negativity of the outcome, which is to somewhat surprising.

Table 12: Outcome by micro-enterprise turnover

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
< 30,001 Euros	BE03					4 (1)
	BE04	(GR04) *	IT03			(5 (1)) *
	BE05					
From 60,000 to 125,000	BE01		IT01 IT02		RO04	4 (3)
From 170,000 to 200,000				NO03 NO04		2 (2)
300.000			IT04	NO01	RO01	3 (2)
Unknown	BE02	GR01 GR02 GR03 GR04		NO02	RO03 RO04	8 (7)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

(*) Turnover figures are not available for any of the Greek cases. However, from the available descriptions, it is relatively clear that GR04 is a microscopic company, while the other three certainly have higher (or much higher) turnovers.

Outcome and motivation of the micro-entrepreneurs

In the first round, we asked all respondents about their motivations for moving their business towards environmental sustainability. The results are presented in the table below per country. Again, codes in bold refer to cases with a positive outcome (as in all subsequent tables).

Table 13: Outcome by motivation

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Save money/return on investment/ further direct economic motivations	BE02	GR01 GR03	IT01 IT03		RO03 RO04	7 (6)
Propensity towards innovation	BE01		IT03	NO01	RO01	10 (8)

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
	BE04			NO02 NO03 NO04	RO02 RO03	
Reputation/social appreciation	BE01 BE03 BE05		IT02 IT04		RO02 RO03 RO04	8 (6)
Other companies in the same area, sector or value chain are doing the same		GR04				1 (0)
It is important to reduce the environmental impact of enterprises	BE01 BE02 BE03 BE04 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03 GR05	IT01 IT02 IT03 IT04	NO01 NO02 NO03 NO04	RO01 RO02 RO03 RO04	21 (15)
Environmental mitigation is a pressing issue that all companies will have to face	BE01		IT02 IT04	NO02 NO04	RO01	6 (6)
To take advantage of a rule or incentive	BE02 BE05					2 (1)
Cooperation/international development	BE04 BE05		IT01 IT02 IT03			5 (2)
Other emotional/cognitive factors	BE02 BE03 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03 GR04	IT04	NO03	RO01 RO02 RO04	12 (9)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

The motivation “It is important to reduce the environmental impact of enterprises” has been highlighted by all the 21 micro-entrepreneurs”. It is possible that some micro-entrepreneurs may have mentioned it ‘automatically’, as the aims of ACCTING and the specific objective of RL4 are well known to all. Nevertheless, there seems to be a unanimous high level of agreement and involvement of these micro-entrepreneurs with the European Green Deal policy aimed at reducing the environmental impact of enterprises on climate change. We could indeed say that the ‘subjective impact’⁴⁴ that can be observed within the case studies is positive.

⁴⁴ ‘Subjective impact’ means the degree of agreement and satisfaction of an involved individual (here each micro-entrepreneur) involved with a policy, initiative or project being assessed. Subjective impact brings in the perspectives of involved individuals and can be used as a precursor of impact.

Second in the ranking is “Other emotional or cognitive factors”. Some examples of this are given below, categorised by main theme. They are all closely related to environmental concerns and represent explanations and variations of the motivation to reduce the environmental impact of their enterprises and personal lives.

Closeness to nature

- “During the winter he works in nature in the mountains (for snowboarding lessons) and he sees that the winters are becoming smaller and smaller and the quantity of snow decreases. He has spent a lot of time in the mountains and connected with people living there” (GR02, man).
- “The personal motivation towards protecting/preserving nature” (RO01, woman).
- “Her beliefs about the importance of preserving natural resources and of living in harmony with nature” (RO04, woman).

Commitment to sustainability

- “She wants to leave a liveable planet to her children. Lastly, her husband is quite engaged in matters of sustainability and being green, and it is an important motivation too” (BE02, woman).
- “It was mainly due to personal beliefs related to sustainability. She wanted to follow the values that she has had all her life and to also insert them in a way when running her company. She feels the moral obligation to do the right thing on her part and wants to be a great role model for her children” (GR03, woman).

Biographic

- “Something that she got from her family circle, and especially from her mother” (GR04, woman).

Social

- “She is also motivated because of her general goal of achieving a positive social impact, consciously choosing more environmentally friendly options whenever financially feasible” (BE03, woman).

Another motivation closely related to environmental issues is “Environmental mitigation is a pressing issue that all companies will have to face”. Only six of the 21 entrepreneurs (BE01, IT02, IT04, NO02, NO04, RO01) indicated this motivation for themselves, but it is worth noting that these are all cases with a positive outcome.

There are also five entrepreneurs motivated by cooperation/international development issues (BE04, BE05, IT01, IT02, IT03), but here there are only two with a positive outcome. This is the worst rate of all in this respect, as if to say that in most of these cases there is a negative outcome because the entrepreneur’s intention is different (development of cooperation) than the one we are interested in (environmental sustainability). Which is not to say that is less valuable, but nonetheless different.

Motivations related to economic concerns (“Save money/return on investment/further direct economic motivations” and “To take advantage of a rule or incentive”) are highlighted by 8 micro-entrepreneurs (BE02, BE05, GR01, GR03, IT01, IT03, RO03, RO04), six of them with a positive outcome. It should be noted that none of the latter highlighted the motivation “Environmental mitigation is a pressing issue that all companies will have to face”.

Three groups of micro-entrepreneurs therefore emerge:

- Those with a strong environmentalist orientation (BE01, IT02, IT04, NO02, NO04, RO01)

- Those who, beyond a basic environmental motivation, show economic motivations (BE02, BE05, GR01, GR03, IT01, IT03, RO03, RO04)
- The third group is made up of the others (BE03, BE04, GR02, GR04, NO01, NO03, RO02), i.e., those who seem to have neither strong environmentalist motivations nor declare economic motivations. Their motivations range from social ones to a propensity towards innovation.

A total of 14 entrepreneurs belong to the first two groups, 12 of them with positive outcomes. Seven entrepreneurs belong to the third group, four of them with a negative outcome.

Motivations referring to the view of other actors (“Reputation/social appreciation” and “Other companies in the same area, sector or value chain are doing the same”) are proposed by nine entrepreneurs. It would therefore seem that almost half of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs are susceptible to the appreciation of their micro-enterprise, which is sometimes explicitly highlighted with reference to their local area (e.g., IT02) or to certain categories of people (e.g., IT04). Among these nine micro-entrepreneurs, the five/sevens versus two/sevens ratio is respected (so, there is no relationship between this motivation and the positivity/negativity of the outcome).

Last but not least, half (10) of the 21 micro-entrepreneurs are motivated by their propensity towards innovation. This motivation can be considered closer to an economic concern (e.g., competitiveness), but also to a social (e.g., social innovation) or a technical/environmental one (e.g., cutting-edge technologies for energy efficiency). Here, too, the five/sevens versus two/sevens ratio is respected: so again, there is no relationship between this motivation and the positivity/negativity of the outcome.

Outcome and values of the micro-entrepreneurs

Not surprisingly, all micro-entrepreneurs say they have a positive attitude towards the environment. However, they do so in different ways:

- BE01 (woman) is very positive about natural environments and is very concerned about the worsening pace of climate change. She does not want to spend the next 40 years of her life working on projects that have questionable impacts in this particular moment in history and in her own life.
- BE04 (woman) is conscious of the environment, but it is more out of a concern for social impact that she embraces environmental objectives.
- IT02 (man) believes in the necessity and compatibility between economic goals (earning money through products and services), and the fulfilment of goals related to social inclusion and environmental sustainability.
- IT04 (woman) has always been environmentally aware and now her thinking is on eco-feminism.
- GR02 (man) considers himself “a son of nature” and says he always did whatever he could to help the environment.
- GR04 has always had a particular sensitivity towards environmental sustainability, and after some personal experiences, this sensitivity grew.
- NO03 (man) is concerned about climate change and the negative effects of global change. He cares about social justice for marginalised people worldwide.
- RO01 (woman) has a positive attitude towards the environment, grounded in her appreciation for nature as opposed to the overcrowded and polluted urban space, which she shares with her husband.

Table 14: Outcome by micro-entrepreneurs' values

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Positive attitudes towards the environment	BE01	GR01	IT01	NO01	RO01	21 (15)
	BE02	GR02	IT02	NO02	RO02	
	BE03	GR03	IT03	NO03	RO03	
	BE04	GR04	IT04	NO04	RO04	
	BE05					
Love of nature, the outdoors, animals	BE01	GR01	IT02	NO01	RO01	12 (11)
		GR02	IT04	NO02	RO03	
		GR03		NO04	RO04	
Global justice/equity/inclusion	BE01					15 (11)
	BE02	GR01	IT02	NO02	RO02	
	BE03	GR04	IT03	NO03	RO04	
	BE04		IT04	NO04		
	BE05					
International development issues (e.g., solidarity)			IT01			9 (6)
	BE04		IT02	NO02		
	BE05		IT03	NO03		
			IT04	NO04		

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

It can also be observed that half of the micro-entrepreneurs (12) say that they love nature, animals or the countryside. Among these latter micro-entrepreneurs, 8 also seem to be interested in social values. To these should be added another seven who have social values but do not seem to be interested in nature as such, most of whom have a negative result. Thus, a total of 15 micro-entrepreneurs expressed social values, more or less linked to environmental values. Finally, there are many more (almost twice as many) who have a global value (e.g., international development, global justice) compared to those who have an environmental value. Thus, entrepreneurs' values only partially reflect their motivations to engage with environmental sustainability.

Outcome and inclusion in networks

As we can see in Table 15 below, 15 out of 21 micro-entrepreneurs have relations with some networks. This is a clear majority, but it should be noted that only in five cases these networks deal with environmental issues. Links with formal and/or informal solidarity networks (11 out of 21) and, to a lesser extent, cultural and/or ethnic networks appear to be much more intensive.

Table 15: Outcome by inclusion in networks

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Inclusion/relation with formal/informal environmental/energy networks	BE01					5 (4)
	BE02			IT04	RO01	
	BE05					

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Inclusion/relation with formal/informal solidarity networks	BE01					
	BE02				NO01	
	BE03	GR04	IT02		NO02	11 (6)
	BE04				NO04	
	BE05					
Inclusion/relation with formal/informal cultural/ethnic networks	BE04		IT01			
	BE05		IT02		RO04	6 (3)
			IT03			
Any network	5(2)	1(0)	4(3)	3(2)	2(2)	15 (9)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

However, it is worth noting that participating in environmental/energy networks is associated with a positive outcome (although it represents only a small fraction of positive cases), and all the corresponding cases are women. Instead, participating in formal/informal solidarity networks is associated with a negative outcome (5 out of 6 cases with a negative outcome are included) and the corresponding cases are proportionally distributed between women and men.

Outcome and crisis of the micro-enterprises

Almost all entrepreneurs (17 out of 21) experienced some kind of crisis. Table 16 summarises the crises they were affected by and the relationship with the outcome. The pandemic crisis is the most frequently mentioned and seems to be associated with a positive outcome.

Table 16: Outcome by micro-enterprise type of crisis

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Affected by the energy crisis	BE05	GR01	IT01	NO02	RO04	7 (5)
			IT02	NO04		
Affected by the pandemic crisis		GR01			RO01	
		GR02	IT02	NO02	RO02	9 (8)
		GR04		NO03	RO03	
Affected by other economic crises	BE01					
	BE02			NO01		3 (2)
Affected by an internal crisis	BE01					
	BE02			NO04		4 (3)
	BE03					
Affected by any crisis	4 (2)	3 (2)	2 (1)	4 (3)	4 (4)	17 (12)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

In fact, this is a false association. The enterprises that were not affected by the pandemic crisis are those that were created after the crisis (e.g., BE04, IT01, IT03, RO04) or that carry out/exercise unrestricted activities during the pandemic. An emblematic case is IT04: it is a bar/pub that is also a

bookshop, which has allowed it to continue operating. Having clarified this aspect (always bearing in mind that we are dealing with extremely low figures), it does not appear that being affected by a crisis (including an energy crisis) or not is relevant to the outcome of achieving environmental sustainability.

Outcome and personal behaviour of the micro-entrepreneur –

Individual changes towards pro-environmental sustainability

The following excerpts are some powerful insights into the personal behaviour (beyond the business) of micro-entrepreneurs and the changes that have been recorded.

- RO01 (woman): There have been parallel initiatives and investments in the private home of the family owning the business, through buying more expensive but energy-saving appliances, and energy-efficient electrical equipment.
- RO03 (woman): She and her husband encouraged their kids to use the bus after school, and they purchased an all-electric car for daily commuting and for trips. Following the pandemic, they also began recycling at home and replaced all the lighting with LED fixtures.
- BE02 (woman): Over the course of the research period, the entrepreneur insulated her personal residence from the outside. Moreover, she already had double-pane windows and an insulated roof. New waste sorting rules went into effect in Flanders in 2024, which means that she is now sorting organic waste separately in her personal life as well. As for mobility, she and her husband would like to acquire an electric personal vehicle.
- BE04 (woman): Main change is linked to behaviour as consumer/mother: she does not buy clothes anymore from big chains where the social / environmental impact of production is likely to be negative.
- BE05 (woman): Change refers to dimensions like green energy and food consumption. She also stated that she recycles now and that she does not drive anymore but walks or takes public transport. With the new store location, it is even possible to simply walk there from her home.
- GR01 (woman): She reports being very methodical when it comes to recycling and even smaller things like switching off all the possible light sources (monitors, etc.) at night. She uses public transport, and she chooses local products when she goes shopping. She also has a bike and uses it for close distances whenever she has the chance. She wants to become even more sustainable, as she wants to purchase an electric scooter to commute to the city centre. She also found that environmental issues are more frequent in her daily discussions.
- GR02 (man): He uses only wooden and paper straws, while he carries his own flask at coffee shops to use for drinking his coffee in order to eliminate the use of one-time paper cups. He is also very conscious about energy consumption at home. He has replaced all light bulbs to LED. All his equipment at home is of last technology to reduce high energy consumption.
- IT01 (man): “Yes. In mobility, both my wife and I use eco-friendly cars even if not electric (hybrid car, *edit.*). We also practise at home the same precautions regarding reducing energy use as much as possible (e.g., all lights are LED at home), moderating heating and air conditioning, waste collection and recycling goods.”
- IT03 (woman): “I pay a lot of attention to water and try not to waste it. Being careful with water comes from my African culture. I also try to recycle as much as possible. I have also tried to do this with regard to nappies for my baby (trying to use cotton nappies which I wash time after

time) but I had to give up because it is too expensive. I also pay a lot of attention to using healthy food products (and from slow-fashion also comes a slow-food approach in nutrition).”

- IT04 (woman): She has “always been environmentally aware”. She always travels by bicycle, is careful about water use and recycling and prefers 0 km food⁴⁵.

Results from 19 cases are reported in the table below (data are missing in two cases from Norway), highlighting five areas of sustainable behaviours.

Table 17: Outcome by personal behaviour/Individual change

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Sustainable mobility	BE01		IT01		RO01	11 (9)
	BE02	GR01	IT02		RO02	
	BE05		IT04		RO03	
					RO04	
Sustainable food consumption	BE05		IT02		RO02	7 (6)
			IT03	NO03	RO04	
			IT04			
Sustainable energy (e.g., adoption of renewable energy and energy efficiency increase)	BE02	GR01	IT01		RO01	11 (8)
	BE05	GR02	IT04	NO03	RO03	
		GR03				
		GR04				
Recycling/waste sorting	BE01	GR01	IT01		RO01	16 (12)
	BE02	GR02	IT02	NO01	RO02	
	BE05	GR03	IT03	NO03	RO03	
		GR04	IT04			
Other (e.g., consumption habits, beyond food)	BE04	GR01	IT04			3 (2)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

⁴⁵ The main characteristic of “0 km food” is that there is a small distance between the place of consumption and the place of production/harvest, meaning it does not go through global trade chains. A product can be called zero-km-product when it travels less than 100 km and is produced ecologically and organically (see: <https://initiativeetdeveloppementcitoyen.org/whats-zero-km-food/>).

As we can see:

- Almost all micro-entrepreneurs report at least some change in their personal behaviour towards pro-environmental sustainability. However, as can be seen from the extracts above, it seems that micro-entrepreneurs adopt/change their behaviour in their own way (or at least, when they talk about it, they tend to emphasise points that are mostly different from what the other micro-entrepreneurs say).
- Individual behaviour seems to be very pro-environmental in the area of “recycling/waste sorting”, and this should depend on the mandatory rules in this regard (more or less respected according to countries and specific territorial areas); somewhat less in relation to sustainable energy and sustainable mobility; and even less in the area of “food consumption” (which seems to be of some importance only in Italy).
- Three micro-entrepreneurs report changes in four of the five considered areas (BE05, GR01, IT04, all women). We have to underline that one of these three cases is associated to a negative outcome.
- 16 micro-entrepreneurs report changes in at least two areas (including three entrepreneurs associated with a negative outcome).

Therefore, based on the last two points, it might seem that entrepreneurs associated with a positive outcome tend to have more pronounced personal pro-environmental behaviour in their everyday lives, but the difference is hardly significant given the low numbers concerned.

Outcome and personal behaviour of partners, employees and clients –

Individual changes towards pro-environmental sustainability

Little can be said in this respect. As seen above, in 10 out of 21 cases the entrepreneur works alone or with only one other person (often on a part-time basis; in some cases, a family member). In addition, some entrepreneurs have little or no knowledge of their employees’ personal behaviour.

However, it is worth reporting some excerpts.

- GR01 (female): Only her one employee who is already very sustainable herself was mentioned. She is vegetarian, she buys only local organic products, and she does recycle at home. She also tries to pass these values to her children who are also very sensitive to the issue according to her.
- GR02 (male): There are three employees, two of them started applying some measures at home, like recycling and energy saving by turning off lights and the air-conditioning at home. One of them also does composting and has switched to wooden toothbrushes and organic shampoos.
- GR03 (female): The only employee started recycling at home and she also now uses organic liquid soap for her dishes.
- IT02 (male): “I would say that everyone who works with me does the same. I cannot say the same about those who are employed in the cooperative (associated to the business)”.
- IT03 (female): As far as she knows, her associate follows a similar approach.
- RO01 (female): Three among the employees also drive personal electric cars, and those who own houses have installed photovoltaics.

- RO02 (male): His employees share his pro-environmental vision, with a focus on limiting food waste.
- RO04 (female): She believes that most of her employees share her perspective on the importance of preserving natural resources in food production.

The main missing piece of information is the relationship between employees' personal behaviour and the sustainable attitudes and practices of the companies they work for. What we have seems to point in the direction of good/increased cohesion within the micro-enterprise (if there are several employees) around pro-environmental values.

Even less is known by the micro-entrepreneurs about clients' behaviour. However, a few excerpts can be reported.

- IT04 (female): Their customers were already aware of environmental problems, but she sees more interest on their part in their events and in the choice of books on the environment. Customers are more interested "perhaps because of the Greta effect". In the neighbourhood, she thinks there is more attention to separate waste management, also thanks to the new dedicated bins for businesses.
- NO03 (male): The customers buy from his shop based on their own personal values and are willing to spend the money to shop what they can from someone who has an environmental profile.
- RO02 (male): Many clients appreciate the measures he introduced; the hope is that they will also take on the interest in limiting food waste that his food company puts forward.

These few examples could show that businesses that are more explicitly pro-environmental will attract clients with those values. However, the examples given are completely insufficient to be able to draw any conclusions in this regard.

3.3.4 Enablers and hinders

As mentioned in Section 1.3, there is an extensive literature on the barriers and drivers that SMEs in general, and micro and small enterprises in particular, face in adopting energy efficiency measures and, more generally, in mitigating their impact on climate change. However, as mentioned above, this literature is not specific to micro-enterprises and even less so to micro-enterprises run by vulnerable groups.

During the three rounds of interviews with the micro-entrepreneurs, several enablers and barriers to behavioural change towards greater sustainability were identified. As seen in Section 2.1, in the first round we looked at, among other things, 'opportunities/support in moving towards environmental sustainability' (e.g., enablers) and 'obstacles/difficulties in moving towards environmental sustainability' (e.g., barriers), and in the second and third rounds we collected updates. In the third round, we also looked at the enablers and hinders encountered in the possible implementation of further measures suggested during the second-round brainstorming.

Enablers and hinders were collected and analysed across three thematic dimensions (using the same scheme as in all other RLs both in RC1 and in RC2): resources of various kinds, relevant social dynamics and structural conditions.

Overall, based on the three rounds of interviews with the 21 micro-entrepreneurs, 88 enablers and 101 hinders can be highlighted (see Table 18). Enablers seem to be mostly related to lack of resources and unsupportive structural conditions, while social dynamics (e.g. "having certain beliefs

and values”, “having significant relationships”, or “being part of a community/network”), also stand out as a generally positive influence on the change process towards environmental sustainability, both overall and for each of the five RL4 countries (with a minimal exception for social dynamics in Greece).

Table 18: Enablers (+) and hinders (-) per type and country

	Belgium		Greece		Italy		Norway		Romania		Total	
	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
Resources	12 (4)	13 (6)	4 (3)	10 (9)	7 (7)	11 (7)	8 (5)	10 (8)	3 (3)	11 (11)	34 (22)	55 (41)
Social Dynamics	13 (4)	4 (2)	3 (2)	4 (3)	13 (11)	1 (1)	8 (6)	3 (2)	10 (10)	0	47 (33)	12 (8)
Structural conditions	2 (1)	7 (4)	0	4 (3)	4 (3)	7 (5)	0	9 (7)	1 (1)	7 (7)	7 (5)	34 (26)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

In the table above, under each figure, we indicate the number of cases with a positive outcome (in bold). We can see that the ratio of five/seven and two/seven between positive and negative outcomes is almost perfectly respected for both enablers and hinders in terms of resources, social dynamics and structural conditions when we look at the cases as a whole. This means that there is no difference between cases with positive and negative outcomes related to the enablers and hinders reported (as well as to several other factors discussed in the previous pages).

This is less true for the positive/negative ratios in the five countries and, as we will see immediately below, when we look at some of the specific facilitators and hinders.

‘Resources’ dimension

The results for the dimension of Resources are reported in Table 19.

Table 19: Enablers (+) and hinders (-) related to Resources, per country

	Belgium		Greece		Italy		Norway		Romania		Total	
	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
Knowledge	BE01 BE02 BE03 BE04 BE05	BE01 BE02 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03 GR04	GR01	IT02 IT03 IT04	IT04	NO03 NO04		RO03 RO04		14 (9)	7 (6)
Money		BE01 BE02 BE03 BE04 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03 GR04		IT04	IT01 IT02 IT03 IT04		NO01 NO02 NO03 NO04		RO01 RO02 RO03 RO04	1 (1)	21 (15)
Education	BE01 BE03			GR03	IT04		NO02		RO02		7 (4)	1 (1)

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
	BE04					
	BE05					
Time	BE01 BE02 BE03 BE04 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03	IT01 IT02 IT03	NO02 NO03 NO04	RO01 RO02 RO03 RO04	0 (14)
Access to political and social actors			IT04 IT01	NO04 NO02		2 (2) 2 (1)
Perceived self-efficacy	BE01 BE03 BE04			NO01 NO03	NO03 RO03	5 (2) 2 (2)
Access to equipment		GR02	IT04 IT01 IT04	NO01 NO02	NO01 RO01	4 (3) 4 (2)
Other resources			IT01		RO01	1 (1) 1 (0)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

In the resources dimension, ‘Money’ is always mentioned as an obstacle by all 21 entrepreneurs. It therefore appears to be a similar problem for both those entrepreneurs with whom we associate a positive outcome and those with whom we associate a negative outcome. It is true that climate change mitigation measures often require companies to invest financial resources, but we have seen that only seven of the 21 entrepreneurs reported significant investments. For them, spending was certainly a problem, just as for others it was the lack of money that prevented them from moving in this direction, as many of them explicitly stated. Below are two examples.

- GR04 (woman) mentioned the lack of resources as the main reason for not looking further into more environmentally sustainable measures for her business. Her difficult financial situation and the fact that her contracts do not yet provide her with a sufficiently stable income are factors that prevent her from implementing further measures to achieve sustainability.
- RO04 (woman) underlined how the lack of financial capital impeded the high expenses involved in thermally insulating the building and in replacing electric appliances with energy-efficient ones.

Similar statements were made by BE04, GR04, IT01, IT03, RO04.

Sometimes the lack of money is linked to the lack of time. According to IT01 (man), “the lack of time, specific opportunities and money has prevented us from doing more to replace the current machinery in the kitchen with more energy-efficient machinery, or to renew the air conditioning, or to carry out an energy audit – he says, adding that – in these circumstances, an increase in turnover would be very important”.

Finally, case IT04 (woman) deserves to be highlighted. She mentions “Money”, not only as a problem but also as an enabling factor. She is the only one of the 21 entrepreneurs who regularly participates in calls for proposals (in many cases securing funding). For her, therefore, “money” also means funding.

We have already mentioned the lack of time. Looking at this in more detail, time is always mentioned as an obstacle in 18 cases (in about the same proportion of positive and negative cases). In general, lack of time is a problem in almost all micro-enterprises. We have seen in Section 2.1 that in 10 out of 21 cases, the entrepreneur works alone or with another person (often on a part-time basis). In four cases, the micro-entrepreneur has another job and can only devote limited time to the micro-enterprise (e.g., BE04 and IT03, both women). It is therefore extremely difficult to find the time needed to make the business more environmentally sustainable.

‘Knowledge’ is highlighted in 16 out of 21 cases (with similar proportions of positive and negative cases); as an enabler in nine cases; as an obstacle in two cases; as both an enabler and an obstacle in five cases.

As we have just mentioned, many entrepreneurs work alone or with very few people and have had to make first-hand efforts to promote changes in relation to environmental sustainability, which have only been possible through their own knowledge, both formal and informal. Two examples are given below.

- BE01 (woman) with a university degree, is quite knowledgeable about possible sustainable interventions she can implement or has already implemented.
- IT02 (man) who never went to school, was able to promote many sustainable actions, based on the knowledge acquired over several years of work in an eco-agricultural cooperative.

At the same time, many entrepreneurs also want to highlight the lack of knowledge that characterises them. ‘Knowledge as an enabler’ and ‘knowledge as an obstacle’ are clearly two sides of the same coin. Emblematic in this respect is IT04, who considers that the fact that she is always informed is definitely a driver for change, but she also feels that she does not have enough technical information to understand what needs to be changed in practice.

Finally, it is worth noting that ‘Knowledge’ is mentioned by 12 out of 13 women and only 3 out of 8 men. It is also mentioned by 12 out of 14 migrants (compared to 4 out of 7 non-migrants).

The issue of education is similar. This factor is mentioned as an enabler by seven entrepreneurs, all of whom have either a university degree (five) or a professional degree (two), and all of whom stress the importance of their educational background.

- BE01 (woman) highlights that her degree in Environmental Change and Management has been a big motivator in wanting to build a sustainable business.
- RO02 (man) thinks that he grew more conscious of the issue of food waste as a result of his university degree in food engineering.

Last but not least, ‘Education’ is mentioned by 7 out of 13 women and only 1 out of 8 men, and by 6 out of 14 migrants (and only 2 out of 7 non-migrants).

Five micro-entrepreneurs perceive their self-efficacy and consider it as an enabler; e.g., BE01 woman, is confident and eager to learn the more practical skills of renovating a building, while two respondents underline its lack as a hinder; e.g., RO03, woman, underlines that she considers herself ineffective to accede to funds opportunities and so, she is renounced.

‘Access to equipment’ is an important enabler for three micro-entrepreneurs (e.g., RO01, woman, whose business is devoted to photovoltaics); and a hinder for three others (e.g., IT01, man, who underlines that he cannot renovate his kitchen in the restaurant – replacing it with a more energy-efficient – since this equipment belongs to the owner of the premises). Finally, IT04, woman, considers this issue both an enabler and a hinder (her business is provided for by useful equipment); however, she cannot set up a photovoltaic system, since they do not own their premises that are in an apartment building.

‘Social dynamics’ dimension

The results for the dimension of social dynamics are reported in Table 20.

Table 20: Enablers (+) and hinders (-) related to social dynamics, per country

	Belgium		Greece		Italy		Norway		Romania		Total	
	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-
Having certain beliefs and values	BE01				IT01				RO01			
	BE02		GR01		IT02		NO02		RO02		17	1
	BE03		GR02		IT03		NO03 NO01		RO03		(14)	(0)
	BE05				IT04		NO04		RO04			
Being part of a community/network	BE01				IT01							
	BE02	BE01			IT02		NO01				13	4
	BE03	BE03	GR04		IT03	IT04	NO04	NO02	RO02		(7)	(3)
	BE04				IT04							
Having significant relationships	BE03						NO01					
	BE04				IT02		NO02		RO01		10	0
	BE05				IT03		NO04		RO03		(6)	
Feelings of social appreciation				GR01	IT02				RO02		7	5
				GR02	IT03				RO03		(6)	(4)
	BE03			GR03	IT04			NO03	RO04			
				GR04								
Other social dynamics		BE01									0	2
		BE05										(1)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

‘Having certain beliefs and values’ is the most frequently focused factor within ‘Social dynamics’, almost always as an enabler (17 cases) and once as an obstacle. Looking at the total of 18 cases, these mentions come in roughly equal proportions from cases with a positive outcome and from cases with a negative outcome.

Values have already been discussed above, highlighting that those related to a sustainable environment and nature, as well as social values (global justice, equity, inclusion, solidarity) are very widespread among the micro-entrepreneurs involved, and most of them consider them as enablers. We can recall, among others:

- BE01 (woman), who is very positive about natural environments and very concerned about the increasing pace of climate change
- GR02 (man), declaring that he did whatever he could to help the environment
- RO01 (woman), who reported a positive attitude towards the environment, grounded in her appreciation for nature.

'Being part of a community/network' appears also as an important enabler (in 13 cases, including 9 migrants). The curious fact here is that the ratio of five to seven and two to seven between cases with positive outcomes and cases with negative outcomes is not respected at all. In fact, this factor is highlighted as an enabler in all six cases associated with a negative outcome and in only seven of the 15 cases associated with a positive outcome.

This can be explained by recalling the networks to which the entrepreneurs are linked, namely (see above the section on 'Outcome and inclusion in networks').

- None of the cases associated with a negative outcome are linked to environmental/energy networks, while all are linked to formal/informal solidarity networks or cultural/ethnic networks, to which entrepreneurs nevertheless attach some importance, even in the context of environmental sustainability.
- The cases associated with a positive outcome are mainly connected to environmental/ energy networks (BE01, BE02 and IT04, all women) and often also to the other kinds of networks.

'Having significant relationships' is associated with ten cases, always as an enabler (7 out of the 13 entrepreneurs with a migrant background). Six cases are associated with a positive outcome, such as:

- IT02 (man), who highlights the importance of his relationship with people in charge of environmental issues in the Municipality of Rome and with an eco-agriculture cooperative linked to his restaurant
- RO01 (woman), who mentions her intensive links with officials and firms in the photovoltaic sector).

Four further cases are associated with a negative outcome. Two examples are given below.

- BE05 (woman), who has some connections to other entrepreneurs that are actively working on environmental sustainability; she believes these will be able to support her in the future.
- NO01 (man), who explained that the community he lives in has several farms and people with similar problems and solutions to his own. Moreover, the cooperative of farmers in Norway can provide other professional help such as veterinary services.

'Feelings of social appreciation' is highlighted as an enabler by seven micro-entrepreneurs, all corresponding to those that mentioned 'reputation/social appreciation' as one of their main motivations for embarking on a path towards environmental sustainability in their business. In addition to the examples cited above (IT02, man, very proud of the appreciation of his green restaurant by the inhabitants of the neighbourhood; and IT04, woman, highlighting the intense relationship with an eco-feminist audience), we can also report RO2 (man), who thinks that many customers appreciate the measures he has introduced in his business; and RO03 (woman), whose customers, she reports, are happy with the eco-friendly improvements in her business, which made the reputation of the business grow.

Conversely, the lack of social appreciation is considered an important hinder by five micro-entrepreneurs, including all the four interviewed in Greece.

‘Structural conditions’ dimension

The results for the dimension of Structural conditions are reported in Table 21.

Table 21: Enablers (+) and hinders (-) related to structural conditions, per country

	Belgium		Greece		Italy		Norway		Romania		Total		
	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	
Social and economic conditions		BE03		GR02 GR03 GR04		IT02 IT04			NO03		RO02 RO04	0	9 (7)
Policies and politics	BE02 BE05	BE01 BE02 BE05		GR01		IT02 IT04			NO01 NO02 NO03	RO01	RO02 RO03 RO04	3 (2)	12 (10)
Physical geography and environment		BE03			IT01 IT02			NO01 NO04				2 (1)	3 (1)
Events and developments		BE01			IT02 IT03			NO02 NO03			RO01	2 (2)	4 (4)
Infrastructure		BE02				IT01 IT03			NO04		RO03	0	5 (4)
Other structural conditions						IT01						0	1 (0)

Cases with positive outcomes are indicated in bold

The most frequently quoted factor in this third category is ‘Policies and politics’, mostly considered as a hinder (by 12 micro-entrepreneurs, ten of which have been associated with a positive outcome), and only by three as an enabler.

In two cases ‘Policies and politics’ are seen as both enabling and hindering. Both cases are in Belgium, where, for example, according to BE02 (woman), policies enabled the entrepreneur to install double-glazed windows to improve energy efficiency. However, policy also acted as a barrier for her for the solar panels she installed in her cooking studio, due to a controversial decision by the Belgian Constitutional Court in 2021. Previously, people in Flanders who produced more energy through solar panels (or other means) than they consumed could feed this energy into the wider energy grid and be compensated for this contribution. In essence, this often meant a lower annual energy bill. However, the court’s ruling essentially removed this option, leaving many solar panel owners feeling disappointed and cheated by the government. As a result, the entrepreneur’s return on investment in the solar panels was not what she had expected.

Entrepreneurs quoting policies and politics only as a hinder highlight these elements.

- Real or supposed shortcomings. RO02, man, hasn’t found a funding programme that he could apply to for financing, at least partly, an investment in a photovoltaic system; similarly, RO04, woman, thinks that the current regulatory and financial support for SMEs that intend to address environmental issues at the national level in Romania is low.

- The lengthy bureaucratic procedures required to obtain any kind of authorisation. IT02, man, refers to the Municipality of Rome and the National Health Agency.
- The pervasiveness of some rules. IT04, woman, refers to the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points/HACCP, a preventive management system in which food safety is addressed through the analysis and control of biological, chemical and physical hazards from raw material production, procurement and handling, to manufacturing, distribution and consumption of the finished product.
- The lack of policies to assist micro-entrepreneurs during deep crises. NO03, man, did not receive any financial support from the government during the energy crisis, which made his financial situation very challenging.
- Costs associated with some policies. NO03 is again critical towards the government for making conditions such as import costs very high – he pays 100% duty on some products – which results in him having to charge a lot for some environmentally friendly products.

'Social and economic conditions' are mentioned (always as an obstacle) in half of the cases (mostly by ten micro-entrepreneurs, eight of them with a positive outcome). Three emblematic cases can be cited.

- According to GR02 (woman), the increase in costs due to inflation in Greece has made it very difficult for a company to survive. In this context, adopting sustainability measures (which usually involve cost/investment) seems very difficult in practice; she believes that it is difficult to plan major investments in environmental issues when faced with such economic uncertainties.
- Also according to RO04 (woman), in the present conditions, it is difficult to plan major environmental investments in the current climate of economic uncertainty.
- According to NO03 (man), policies such as high import costs generate very harsh economic conditions in which it is very difficult to proceed towards the environmental sustainability of one's business.

'Infrastructure' too is quoted always as hinder, but only by five micro-entrepreneurs, and that is in terms of the lack of certain infrastructures. So, IT03 (woman), who chose to use ships for the transport of textile products between West-Africa and Italy to pollute less, complains about the lack of adequate shipping lines; while BE02 (woman) has a practical concern about acquiring an electric truck for her business. Apart from the cost, it would be impractical for longer distances, since recharging an electric truck takes a lot more time (at least for now) than refuelling a conventional truck.

Finally, it should be noted that the factor 'events and developments' is only mentioned by entrepreneurs with a positive outcome. In two cases it is mentioned as an enabler (e.g., IT03, woman, stresses the importance of events such as the fairs organised by her association of migrants in promoting her "slow fashion" approach). In four cases it is mentioned as an obstacle (e.g., RO01, man, denounced that the plan to replace petrol cars with electric cars is currently blocked because the incentives offered by the Romanian government for the purchase of electric cars have been cut by more than half since the beginning of 2024).

Enablers, hindlers and vulnerable profiles

Vulnerability profiles were barely mentioned in the previous pages. This was not an omission. There is little data on the two main vulnerability profiles within the 21 entrepreneurs: gender (13 women and 8 men) and people with a migrant background (14 out of 21). People are often distributed in the same proportions in relation to each of the covered issues, but there are some exceptions.

Gender

- The factor 'Knowledge' is mentioned by 12 out of 13 women; and only by 3 out of 8 men.
- The factor 'Education' is mentioned by 7 out of 13 women; and only by 1 out of 8 men.
- Entrepreneurs highlighting the factor 'Being part of a community/network' and having linkages with environmental networks (as well as a positive outcome) are all women.

Migrant background

Entrepreneurs with a migrant background were more likely to consider 'Knowledge', 'Education', 'Being part of a community/network', and 'Having significant relationships' as important factors.

Looking now at the other vulnerability profiles, although the numbers are very small, nothing seems to stand out except for the high propensity to consider 'Reputation/social appreciation of people' important, associated with the 'Age' vulnerability profile (5 out of 6).

Conclusions and Discussions

4. Overall conclusions and discussion

4.1 Overall conclusions with respect to the RL specific research question

The RL4 research question (see Section 2.1) has been drafted as follows: "How do the most vulnerable entrepreneurs change their behaviour in the management of their enterprises, and broadly, towards climate change mitigation in connection to the planning and adoption of pro-environmental measures? Which are the enabling and the hindering factors in this process?"

This question has been discussed extensively and thoroughly in the previous pages. Let us summarise some of the findings.

Vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs address the issue of environmental sustainability in their businesses

1. While it is probably true that most micro-entrepreneurs have neither the skills nor the interest to address the issue of environmental sustainability in their business⁴⁶ (and probably even more so vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs), the 21 entrepreneurs involved are living proof that it can be done. Nor is it something exceptional. As a matter of fact:
 - i. It appears possible in many kinds of business, from little hotels to textile workshops; from bookshops to rural enterprises; from small retailers to restaurants; from bakeries to jewellers.
 - ii. It is possible also in informal enterprises having a small turnover.

⁴⁶ Hitchens, D., Thankappan, S., Trainor, M., Clausen, J., & De Marchi, B. (2005). Cit.

- iii. And also, in business run by entrepreneurs who never went to school.
 - iv. It is possible for micro-entrepreneurs with different kinds of vulnerability profiles (at least those covered in this RL4).
 - v. And who have experienced different types of crises (pandemic, energy, but also internal ones).
2. The measures that are conceived, designed, adopted and then maintained by the various entrepreneurs are heterogeneous and, as a whole, tend to cover almost everything that can be imagined for such small businesses. These measures cover various domains: energy efficiency, energy transition towards renewables, energy control and audit, waste sorting, used materials (from eliminating plastic to the exclusive use of biodegradable materials), waste recycling, adopting food/fabrics ethic principles, sustainable mobility, awareness-raising activities (eco-feminist projects included).
 3. Most of the entrepreneurs who address the issue of environmental sustainability tend to take an integrated/multiple approach, looking at the different measures that should be taken in the different facets of their business. Then, of course, due to time or resource constraints, many things are postponed or not implemented at all. But their approach tends to be constant rather than occasional (i.e., environmental measures are hardly ever one-offs).
 4. What will be postponed or not carried out at all are, above all, measures that require significant investment. Both for lack of resources and for many other reasons (because you live in a condominium, because you are not the owner of the premises, because there are procedural constraints – e.g., landscape constraints).
 5. At first sight, all entrepreneurs appear to be open to suggestions from others and to cooperate effectively with other actors. On the practical side, there is a (perhaps somewhat fluid) distinction between those who actually tend to take suggestions and put them into practice (and even cooperate with other people) and those who, on the other hand, tend to believe (even in the area of environmental sustainability) that they already know which way to go).

Vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs are often successful. How does it happen?

6. Vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who address the environmental sustainability of their business often do so successfully (a positive outcome was assigned to 15 out of 21 cases), regardless of their sector of activity. Again, there is no relationship between the level of education of the micro-entrepreneur and the positive or negative outcome, nor does the turnover of the business influence the positive or negative outcome (although microscopic or small budgets can be a clear obstacle).
7. How can it happen? In this context, it is useful to look at the motivations of the micro-entrepreneurs who are addressing the issue of environmental sustainability in their business and to look more closely at those who are doing so successfully (positive outcome). Three groups of micro-entrepreneurs can be identified:
 - i. Those with a strong environmentalist motivation⁴⁷; all (six) got a positive outcome.

⁴⁷ As a reminder: “It is important to reduce the environmental impact of enterprises”.

- ii. Those, who, beyond a basic environmental motivation (important to reduce impact) but not a higher-level environmental awareness⁴⁸, show economic motivations⁴⁹; almost all (6 out of 8) got a positive outcome.
- iii. Those who, in addition to a basic environmental motivation, have mainly social motivations (achieving a positive social impact, contributing to international development) or a propensity towards innovation; seven entrepreneurs belong to this group, four of them getting a negative outcome.

In line with what has already been noted in some studies⁵⁰, it seems that entrepreneurs have a balance between social, environmental and economic concerns at the basis of their motivation system, so that an environmental perspective is detrimental to a social perspective and vice versa (although the economic purpose cannot be absent). Therefore, those who are concerned about international development and other societal issues (but also have a high propensity to innovate) seem to be less able to focus their efforts and resources (and thus be successful) in addressing environmental sustainability in their business.

Moreover, looking at the system of reference values, what has just been said is confirmed: entrepreneurs with prevailing social values are mostly associated with a negative outcome.

8. Another aspect that seems to be a driver of success is the existence of relationships with networks dealing with environmental issues. All five entrepreneurs who had such relationships achieved a positive outcome. Relations with formal/informal solidarity networks (11 out of 21) and, to a lesser extent, cultural/ethnic networks (6 out of 21) are much more likely to be associated with a negative outcome.
9. In order to better understand how it can happen that micro-entrepreneurs successfully engage in environmental sustainability, it might also be useful to look at the personal behaviour of the entrepreneurs, beyond their business practices. Although for a micro-entrepreneur there is often little distinction between business and family/private life⁵¹, it is still possible to point out that entrepreneurs who are associated with a positive outcome seem to be more likely to adopt more pronounced personal pro-environmental behaviours in their everyday life. However, it should be noted that almost all micro-entrepreneurs report at least some change towards pro-environmental sustainability in their personal behaviour (in their private life).
10. Finally, we have been able to say very little about individual changes in the partners, employees and clients of micro-enterprises towards pro-environmental sustainability. We have only been able to present a small number of excerpts, but they give the impression that the adoption of a path towards environmental sustainability in a micro-enterprise can still have an impact on the individual behaviour of the people working there (beyond those interviewed in ACCTING) and even on their clients.

⁴⁸ As a reminder: "It is important to reduce the environmental impact of enterprises".

⁴⁹ As a reminder: "Save money/return on investment/ further direct economic motivations" and/or "To take advantage of a rule or incentive".

⁵⁰ E.g. Brockhaus, S., Fawcett, S. E., Knemeyer, A. M., & Fawcett, A. M. (2017). Motivations for environmental and social consciousness: Reevaluating the sustainability-based view. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 933-947. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0959652616320820>

⁵¹ E.g. Munoz, J. M. S. (Ed.). (2010). *Contemporary microenterprise: Concepts and cases*. Edward Elgar Publishing. Orel, M., Lukes, M., & Zouhar, J. (2024). Fostering wellbeing and satisfaction for micro-entrepreneurs: the role of co-working spaces. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 31(8), 148-167. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381986771_Fostering_wellbeing_and_satisfaction_for_micro-entrepreneurs_the_role_of_coworking_spaces.

Meeting facilitating and hindering factors

11. It should be reminded that enablers and hindering factors have been collected and analysed across three thematic dimensions: (i) resources of various kind; (ii) relevant social dynamics, and (iii) structural conditions. Globally speaking, hindering factors seem to mostly revolve around lack of resources and unsupportive structural conditions, while social dynamics stand out as a generally positive influence on the changing process towards environmental sustainability.
12. In the resources dimension, the lack of money (quoted by all 21 entrepreneurs) and the lack of time (quoted by 18 micro-entrepreneurs) appear as very important hindering factors, often associated (i.e., highlighted together) by many micro-entrepreneurs. In one case, 'Money' is mentioned also as an enabler (e.g., getting funds from projects, subsidies). 'Knowledge' is mostly mentioned as an enabler, but also as a hinder (e.g., the lack of knowledge that characterises many micro-entrepreneurs). The 'Education' factor is less quoted by micro-entrepreneurs, albeit in an almost similar way.
13. Among social dynamics, 'Having certain beliefs and values' is the factor most frequently focused on (as an enabler) by the 17 micro-entrepreneurs, highlighting values related to a sustainable environment, closeness to nature, as well as social values (global justice, equity, inclusion, solidarity). 'Being part of a community/network' also appears as an important enabler (13 cases), as already discussed above. 'Having significant relationships' is associated with ten cases, always as an enabler. Micro-entrepreneurs highlighted the importance of relationships with other firms, people working on renewable energy or local authorities. A 'Feeling of social appreciation' is highlighted as an enabler by seven micro-entrepreneurs, who are the same as those who mentioned 'Reputation/social appreciation' as one of their main motivations for embarking on a path towards environmental sustainability in their business. Conversely, four other micro-entrepreneurs complained about the lack of social appreciation.
14. The main factor mentioned under 'structural conditions' is 'policies and politics', which is mostly seen as an obstacle (by 12 micro-entrepreneurs), while three micro-entrepreneurs mentioned it as an enabler. Indeed, policies related to energy efficiency and the transition to renewable energy, depending on their specific content, sometimes help micro-entrepreneurs and sometimes they can even hinder them. Other barriers are related to bureaucratic procedures and/or costs for obtaining permits, and the pervasiveness of some regulations or, conversely, regulatory shortcomings. 'Social and economic conditions' are mentioned as an obstacle by ten micro-entrepreneurs, mostly referring to the harsh economic conditions (e.g., due to inflation) which make it very difficult to move towards the environmental sustainability of one's business. The lack of infrastructure (mainly related to transport) is another obstacle, according to five micro-entrepreneurs.

Vulnerability profiles

15. It should also be noted that, for almost all the vulnerability criteria, the ratio of positive to negative outcomes is five/seven to two/seven (15 positive and 6 negative outcomes for the 21 micro-entrepreneurs), following general results:
 - i. Gender 9 versus 4
 - ii. Migrant/nationality 9 versus 5
 - iii. Age 4 versus 2.

16. However, some gender-specific trends have been highlighted in this report and may be recalled here.
- i. Women are more interested than men in implementing (or at least considering) measures suggested by other entrepreneurs; men are more often only seemingly open (often thinking that they have already done or know what to do in their business).
 - ii. Similarly, beyond the talk, women appear to be more concretely interested in incentives, subsidies and other opportunities than men.
 - iii. The cases of real and effective openness to external parties are all from female entrepreneurs.
 - iv. Conversely, the only two cases of lack of confidence in the sustainability of the measures adopted (indeed in the sustainability of their business) are also women micro-entrepreneurs.
 - v. All entrepreneurs cooperating with environmental networks are women.

Looking at the main enablers/hinders:

- vi. The entrepreneurs highlighting the factor 'being part of a community/network' are all women.
 - vii. The factor 'Kkknowledge' is mentioned by 12 out of 13 women; and only by 3 out of 8 men.
 - viii. The factor "education" is mentioned by 7 out of 13 women; and only by 1 out of 8 men.
17. Looking at the other vulnerability profiles, there were less evidence. As mentioned in the previous pages:
- i. Migrants have a higher propensity to consider important the factors 'knowledge', 'education', 'being part of a community/network', and 'having significant relationships'.
 - ii. People associated with the 'age' vulnerability profile manifest a higher propensity towards the enabler 'reputation/social appreciation'.

4.2 Overall conclusions with respect to implementing a gender+ inclusive Green Deal

As mentioned above, the action research carried out under RL4 has shown that:

- There are vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs who are addressing the environmental sustainability of their business. There are many transformations underway.
- Most of them are able to do so, often in a sustainable way.
- However, they face a number of obstacles.
- Moreover, this transformation process is linked to a change in behaviour, not only of the entrepreneurs in the management of their business and in their everyday life, but also, in some way, of the people who live in contact with their business (partners, employees and sometimes even customers).

So far, the European Green Deal and all related plans at European and national level (see also Section 1.2) do not include specific measures to support the environmental sustainability of vulnerable micro-enterprises. Policies to improve energy efficiency and, more generally, the environmental sustainability of enterprises tend to focus on larger enterprises. There are specific policies for SMEs

(including micro-enterprises), but these are almost never related to climate issues, but mainly to more general issues such as business start-up, management, employability or vocational training.

Among policymakers (including the European Commission), there often seems to be a lack of linkages between those dealing with the environmental sustainability of enterprises and those dealing with social inclusion policies in relation to enterprises, who are usually interested in youth, women and migrant SMEs. Related policies and projects should be brought together as much as possible, and all this should contribute to strengthening and improving an effective gender+ inclusive Green Deal in relation to business.

4.3 Expected sustainability of impacts and changes measured

As we have seen in the Section 2.1, one of the determinants for assessing the positivity or negativity of the outcome is the micro-entrepreneurs' "confidence in the sustainability of the adopted measures". As we have seen, almost all (17 out of 21 micro-entrepreneurs) are very confident. As mentioned above, the remaining four micro-entrepreneurs are mostly not confident because they have not adopted any environmental measures or because they do not have enough confidence in the sustainability of their business. So, from this (small) perspective, the sustainability of the impact appears to be total.

However, it is clear that the issue is much broader. Firstly, we are only reporting the subjective opinions of individuals (who are also part of the picture). And secondly, the sustainability of the measures taken is only part of the issue. The supposedly pro-environmental behaviour of the entrepreneur in the management of his or her business could be reversed for many other reasons, such as possible crises in the context in which he or she operates, internal crises within his or her micro-business, personal and family issues, etc. In reality, there are no elements to fully assess the sustainability of the impact. Here we have only one indicator, albeit a very positive one.

4.4 Replicability and scalability of the actions studied

The measures adopted and implemented to improve environmental sustainability in the 21 cases are certainly replicable and have already been replicated in dozens of other companies. Of course, replication requires adaptation. No measure can simply be copied but should be adapted to the receiving context (another micro-enterprise operating in a different social, economic, political and environmental context).

Through the brainstorming session included in the second round of interviews with all 21 micro-entrepreneurs (see Section 1.2), we can say that ACCTING contributed to the replicability of environmental measures already adopted elsewhere, as they should facilitate the replication of environmental sustainability schemes in other micro-enterprises. During the third round, we noticed that only in rare cases something was replicated, but in many other cases the foundations were laid (e.g., through feasibility studies, discussions with consultants or administrative actions) so that such replication could take place in the more or less near future.

4.5 Policy crossovers

The entrepreneurial activities implemented by the 21 micro-entrepreneurs involved concern several sectors (see Table 2 in Section 2.1). More importantly, some of the measures adopted (see Table 3 in Section 2.1) touch on some of the crossovers highlighted in Table 22, below.

The most cited crossovers can be traced back to 'sustainable products' (elimination of plastic in favour of wood, glass, paper and other biodegradable products, which has been discussed many times,

especially in the cases of hotels and restaurants) and to ‘renovated & energy-efficient buildings and equipment’ (see here the cases including insulation of floors, roofs, walls, facades or the purchase of more efficient equipment for heating, air conditioning or cooking). A certain number of overlaps concern cases related to ‘healthy and affordable food’ (e.g., recycling food and minimising food waste) and ‘sustainable mobility’ (e.g., reducing emissions by shipping goods by cargo ship rather than by plane and using electric cars/bikes for delivery) (See RL5, RL7 and RL reports).

Table 22: Crossovers, per country

	Belgium	Greece	Italy	Norway	Romania	Total
Sustainable products	BE02 BE05	GR01 GR02 GR03	IT02 IT03 IT04	NO02 NO03 NO04	RO02 RO04	13
Clean & healthy environment	BE02	GR03	IT01 IT02 IT04		RO02 RO04	7
Clean energy & technology	BE02				RO01	2
Renovated & energy-efficient buildings and equipment	BE01	GR01 GR02	IT01 IT02 IT04	NO01	RO02 RO03	9
Competitive & resilient industry	BE05		IT03			2
Healthy and affordable food		GR02	IT01 IT02 IT04	NO04	RO02 RO03 RO04	8
Future-proof jobs and skills						0
Sustainable mobility/transport	BE05	GR01	IT03		RO01 RO02 RO03	6

4.6 Research Limitations: A critical discussion of the choice of cases and research design

The research design we adopted was probably the only one possible under the given conditions (more specifically, the enormous difficulties in recruiting micro-entrepreneurs, especially those who are vulnerable). Certainly, however, only being interested in micro-entrepreneurs who were addressing the issue of environmental sustainability (at least at the design stage) was not only a real area of interest (see Section 1.3), but also a limitation. It could be considered appropriate to include those who have not done anything in this respect and, above all, do not consider themselves capable of doing anything. Or, alternatively, to include and compare both types of micro-entrepreneurs. This would probably have allowed to identify more intersectional profiles (probably more frequent among micro-entrepreneurs in worse conditions).

We have adopted a processual (we cannot say longitudinal⁵²) approach to monitor changes in the selected micro-enterprises (and thus changes in the behaviour of the entrepreneurs in the management of their business and beyond) as they move towards greater environmental sustainability. However, the time available (up to 8 months) was too short for a micro-enterprise to make significant progress towards environmental sustainability. A significant period would have been at least one year/one and a half, but we didn't have so much time in the context of ACCTING RC2. So, we decided to extend the survey period and ask the entrepreneurs, in the first round, about any changes over the past year/year and a half.

The number of entrepreneurs surveyed is very small considering that there are hundreds of thousands of micro-entrepreneurs in Europe and that the number of micro-entrepreneurs involved in environmental sustainability should be at least tens of thousands. Perhaps it would have been better to simplify the consultation (a simple questionnaire to be filled in once) and to significantly increase the number of micro-entrepreneurs to be surveyed (e.g., 200 or 300 micro-entrepreneurs per country). We would have increased the representativeness of the sample, but we would have had to forego several in-depth analyses.

Beyond that – and this is the most important aspect – it would still have been an unworkable choice. There are no (even rough) lists of micro-enterprises run by vulnerable people from which to draw the sample. We would therefore have had to recruit through intermediaries and informal contacts. With such an approach, it was already difficult to recruit four or five micro-entrepreneurs per country, let alone 200 or 300.

For all these reasons, we believe that, despite certain limitations, it would have been very difficult, given the time and resources available, to proceed differently.

4.7 Discussion of research gaps and avenues for future research

The first research gap, already highlighted in the section above, is exemplified by the absence, among the 21 micro-entrepreneurs involved in second Research Cycle (the same was true of the 50 entrepreneurs recruited for the narrative collection in RC1), of those micro-entrepreneurs who, due to objective constraints or lack of interest, are unable or unwilling to engage with environmental issues.

They represent the vast majority of micro-entrepreneurs but, as we have just said, they are difficult to locate and recruit for an interview, and this represents a general gap in research, which consistently fails to address the intersection of micro-entrepreneurship, vulnerable entrepreneurship and environmental sustainability. As discussed above, we preferred to recruit the 'good guys' (in 15 cases 'excellent guys'), so to speak, and therefore not be able to answer questions about what happens to and what works with those who are not environmentally aware.

A second gap (still dependent on recruitment) is the lack of intersectional profiles. This is perhaps a specific feature of this line of research, but we still need to strive to include more intersectionally vulnerable people (see Table 1 in Section 1.3). We are particularly lacking some of the more extreme forms of marginality.

⁵² In a longitudinal study, researchers repeatedly examine the same individuals to detect any changes that might occur over a period of time. Longitudinal studies are a type of correlational research in which researchers observe and collect data on a number of variables without trying to influence those variables (see Lauren T. (2023). Longitudinal Study | Definition, Approaches & Examples. Available at: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/longitudinal-study/>).

This gap will not be easy to overcome in future research. Probably, to interact positively with the most vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs, action research approaches should be emphasised. Here, we limited ourselves to brainstorming with suggestions for actions to be taken, possible (funding) opportunities to be explored and actors to be contacted. In this respect, the ongoing ACCTING Pilot Action 4 (PA4, inspired by RL4) “Supporting Roma micro-entrepreneurs in Albania towards better environmental sustainability” could be an example of how to reach the most vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs.

It would be important to maintain and probably intensify the study of the ongoing transformations in micro and small enterprises. In both RC1 and RC2 we interacted with each micro-entrepreneur individually. The transformation process could be more fruitfully observed in the interaction of micro-entrepreneurs with each other and also within the networks to which they are linked, and finally in their interaction with other actors with whom they sometimes interact (e.g., business associations, local authorities).

A final avenue for future research on vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs that was highlighted in this report concerns the lack of connection between policies pertaining to the social inclusion of vulnerable micro-entrepreneurs and policies aimed at improving the environmental sustainability of micro-enterprises. A question that is inherent to the sometimes limited consideration of the possible negative social effects of measures to increase environmental sustainability (which, after all, is one of ACCTING’s main concerns).

References

- Aracil-Jordá, J., Clemente-Almendros, J. A., Jiménez-Zarco, A. I., & González-González, I. (2023). Improving the social performance of women-led microenterprises: The role of social media marketing actions. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 191, 122484. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122484>
- Arul Paramanandam, D., & Packirisamy, P. (2015). An empirical study on the impact of micro enterprises on women empowerment. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 9(4), 298-314. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-02-2015-0029>
- Brockhaus, S., Fawcett, S. E., Knemeyer, A. M., & Fawcett, A. M. (2017). Motivations for environmental and social consciousness: Reevaluating the sustainability-based view. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 933-947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.11.048>
- Carranza, E., Dhakal, C., & Love, I. (2018). Female entrepreneurs: How and why are they different? *The World Bank*. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/400121542883319809/pdf/Female-Entrepreneurs-How-and-Why-are-They-Different.pdf>
- Cheba, K., Bąk, I., Szopik-Depczyńska, K., & Ioppolo, G. (2022). Directions of green transformation of the European Union countries. *Ecological Indicators*, 136, 108601. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.108601>
- Corsini, F., Appio, F. P., & Frey, M. (2019). Exploring the antecedents and consequences of environmental performance in microenterprises: The case of the Italian craft beer industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 138, 340-350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.08.024>
- Crehan, P. (2021). A business service ecosystem supporting the transition to net zero. Presented at *The ISPIM Innovation Conference – Innovating Our Common Future, Berlin, Germany*. Proceedings by LUT Scientific and Expertise Publications.
- Crittenden, V. L., Crittenden, W. F., & Ajjan, H. (2019). Empowering women microentrepreneurs in emerging economies: The role of information communications technology. *Journal of Business Research*, 98, 191-203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusres.2019.01.047>
- David, A., Terstriep, J., Schäfer, S., & Schmidt, A. G. (2024). An intersectional perspective on the impacts and responses of entrepreneurs during the COVID-19 pandemic in Germany. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 14657503241258933. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14657503241258933>
- Ehlers, T. B., & Main, K. (1998). Women and the false promise of microenterprise. *Gender & Society*, 12(4), 424-440. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0891243298012004004>
- Gurung, P., & Sarkar, S. (2022). Sustainability of microenterprises: An empirical investigation. *Indian Journal of Economics*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372751525_Sustainability_of_Microenterprises_An_Empirical_Investigation
- Guzman, J., & Kacperczyk, A. O. (2019). Gender gap in entrepreneurship. *Research Policy*, 48(7), 1666-1680. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2019.03.003>

Harima, A. (2022). Transnational migration entrepreneurship during a crisis: Immediate response to challenges and opportunities emerging through the COVID-19 pandemic. *Business and Society Review*, 127(S1), 223–251. <https://doi.org/10.1111/basr.12242>

Hitchens, D., Thankappan, S., Trainor, M., Clausen, J., & De Marchi, B. (2005). Environmental performance, competitiveness and management of small businesses in Europe. *Tijdschrift voor economische en sociale geografie*, 96(5), 541-557. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0327.2005.00313.x>

Johansson, M. T., & Thollander, P. (2018). A review of barriers to and driving forces for improved energy efficiency in Swedish industry—recommendations for successful in-house energy management. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82, 618–628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2017.09.052>

Khan, S. J. M. (2020). Youth entrepreneurship in small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In *Talent Development for Youth Entrepreneurship* (pp. 101-118). UUM Press.

Lassalle, P., & Shaw, E. (2021). Trailing wives and constrained agency among women migrant entrepreneurs: An intersectional perspective. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 45(6), 1496–1521. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1042258720915444>

Lateh, M., Hussain, M. D., & Halim, M. S. A. (2017). Micro enterprise development and income sustainability for poverty reduction: A literature investigation. *International Journal of Business and Technopreneurship*, 7(1), 23-38.

Lauren, T. (2023). Longitudinal study: Definition, approaches & examples. *Scribbr*. <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/longitudinal-study>

Maggino, F. (2004). I modelli di scaling. Confronto tra ipotesi complesse per la misurazione del soggettivo (Scaling models. Comparison of complex hypotheses for measuring the subjective). *Firenze University Press, Archivio E-Prints, Firenze*.

Meath, C., Linnenluecke, M., & Griffiths, A. (2015). Barriers and motivators to the adoption of energy savings measures for SMEs: The case of the ClimateSmart Business Cluster Program. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 112(5), 3597-3604. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.08.085>

Mulira, F., & Ndaba, Z. (2016). Gender and disability: An intersectionality perspective of microenterprise learning among women with disabilities in Uganda. *Africagrowth Agenda*, 2016(10), 14-17.

Munoz, J. M. S. (Ed.). (2010). *Contemporary microenterprise: Concepts and cases*. Edward Elgar Publishing.

Nulkar, G. (2014). SMEs and environmental performance—A framework for green business strategies. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 133, 130-140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.195>

Orel, M., Lukes, M., & Zouhar, J. (2024). Fostering wellbeing and satisfaction for micro-entrepreneurs: The role of co-working spaces. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 31(8), 148-167. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSBED-09-2023-0273>

Palm, J. (2009). Placing barriers to industrial energy efficiency in a social context: A discussion of lifestyle categorisation. *Energy Efficiency*, 2(3), 263–270. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12053-009-9042-1>

Qureshi, I., Bhatt, B., Sutter, C., & Shukla, D. M. (2023). Social entrepreneurship and intersectionality: Mitigating extreme exclusion. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 38(2), 106283.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusvent.2023.106283>

Rahman, M. Z., Ullah, F., & Thompson, P. (2018). Challenges and issues facing ethnic minority small business owners: The Scottish experience. *The International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Innovation*, 19(3), 177–193. <https://doi.org/10.5367/ijei.2018.0349>

Reuter, S., Lackner, P., & Brandl, G. (2021). Mapping SMEs in Europe: Data collection, analysis and methodologies for estimating energy consumption at country levels. *H2020 LEAP4SME*.

Revenga, A., & Dooley, M. (2020). What works for women micro entrepreneurs: A meta-analysis of recent evaluations to support female entrepreneurship. *Brookings Institution*.

<https://www.brookings.edu/articles/what-works-for-women-microentrepreneurs>

Rogulj, I. (2024). Discussion paper: What determinants of microenterprises influence their energy vulnerability? *IEECP*.

Shahzady, R. (2024). The role of social media for microentrepreneurship of young startups.

International Journal of Law and Policy, 2(6), 10-22. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10542-020-01548-1>

Sorrell, S., Mallett, A., & Nye, S. (2011). Barriers to industrial energy efficiency: A literature review.

UNIDO. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2010.10.021>

Tessema, G. (2015). Assessing the challenges of youth entrepreneurship in micro and small scale enterprises: The case of North Gondar zone, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Applied Research*, 1(12), 53-64.

Thollander, P., Backlund, S., Trianni, A., & Cagno, E. (2013). Beyond barriers: A case study on driving forces for improved energy efficiency in the foundry industries in Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Spain, and Sweden. *Applied Energy*, 111, 636–643.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2013.05.036>

Trianni, A., Cagno, E., & Farné, S. (2016). Barriers, drivers, and decision-making process for industrial energy efficiency: A broad study among manufacturing small and medium-sized enterprises. *Applied Energy*, 162, 1537–1551. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.02.078>

Triguero, A., Moreno-Mondéjar, L., & Davia, M. A. (2011). Drivers of different types of eco-innovation in European SMEs. *Ecological Economics*, 92, 25–33.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2013.04.009>

Verheul, I., Stel, A. V., & Thurik, R. (2006). Explaining female and male entrepreneurship at the country level. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 18(2), 151-183.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/08985620600564455>

Yoganandan, G., & Vignesh, T. (2017). Challenges of young entrepreneurs. *Asia Pacific Journal of Research*, 1(56), 112-115.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344336561_CHALLENGES_OF_YOUNG_ENTREPRENEURS

